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List of Organizations and Abbreviations

AAL Active and Assisted Living

BCR Brussels Capital Region

CAB Citizen Advisory Board

CDTI Spanish Centre for the Development of Industrial Technology (project partner)

FFG Austrian Research Promotion Agency (project partner)

LBG Ludwig Boltzmann Gesellschaft

NHS National Health Service

RCN Research Council Norway (project partner)

RCL Research Council Lithuania (project partner)

RFO Research Funding Organization

RDI Research, Development and Innovation

R&D Research and Development

R&I Research and Innovation

RI Research Integrity

RIS3 (Regional) Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisations

SSH Social Sciences and Humanities

TA CR Technology Agency of the Czech Republic (former project partner)

TUD Technical University Delft (project partner)

TAFTIE The European Network of leading national innovation agencies

UEFISCDI Romanian Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development & Innovation Funding (project partner)

ZSI Center for Social Innovation (project partner)

Executive Summary

The PRO-Ethics project is geared towards the development of an *Ethics Framework and Guidelines* supporting the ethical implementation of participatory processes in the activities of research funding organizations (RFOs). This core output is developed in an iterative process and tested in the context of 10 participatory pilots, which also served to identify best practices, and find levers to adapt institutional processes and embed the learnings of the project in regional and national R&I ecosystems across Europe. These pilots have been implemented in two phases. The present deliverable gives insight into the processes of pilot phase II, as well as the concrete lessons that could be extracted from them.

Pilot data has been collected through various instruments, including structured activity reports, reflection and evaluation workshops, pilot stories, and narrations provided in the context of regular consortium calls, collected in the form of minutes and transcripts. In addition, two workshops with external stakeholders were held and their insights documented in the present deliverable.

These data indicate various tensions and points of friction, as well as possible solutions and recommendations related to the implementation of participatory activities. Broadly speaking, these pertain e.g. to structural barriers, limited resources, time constraints, limited expertise, and processual uncertainties on the side of the implementing organizations. Regarding participants, access to the field, understanding and addressing stakeholders' needs and expectations, emergent role conflicts and appropriate engagement formats came up as examples of relevant issues impacting the success of a pilot.

In general, the project's pilot partners found it helpful to have clarity on the process, its aims, scope, and limitations, and the roles of each partner in the project, while stressing the importance of communicating these clearly and transparently to participants. Including all relevant stakeholders as early as possible in the process to avoid later friction or even interference was also an important learning from the project, as was the benefit of engaging external experts when the RFO is missing certain knowledge or capacities. The importance of developing an understanding of the participant community and choosing appropriate recruitment and engagement formats that also fit the goals of the process and the available resources was also stressed. In any case, it is important to avoid tokenism and allow for meaningful participation to implement engagement practices in an ethically sound manner. Overall, participatory processes necessitate continuous (re-)negotiations of processes, roles and responsibilities that require considerable time, effort, financing, and other resources. Thus, the available resources, institutional support, and established organizational structures need to be carefully considered when planning a participatory process, as they impact its potential scope and any potential leeway in its implementation.

The key recommendations covered in this document can be summarized as such:

- ▶ Before planning any participatory activity, carefully consider the resources and institutional support you have at your disposal, as well as the established structures of your organization.
- ▶ Involve key stakeholders such as politicians and other decision-makers from the very beginning and maybe even seek contractual agreements based on detailed plans with all parties.
- ▶ Be realistic and pragmatic regarding the scope of your participatory process – regarding both the organizational and the participant level. Consider what is feasible in terms of recruitment and engagement methodology, breadth of the target group, and process goals.
- ▶ Employing a professional recruitment company can be helpful in cases internal time and expertise is insufficient to implement this task. Providing compensation and other means of support (e.g. childcare) can help secure a wider representation. If you cannot reach your target group through your initial approach, be flexible and try other approaches.

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- ▶ Identify and address potentially time-consuming administrative processes that may act as barriers to participation, such as payment processing procedures for compensation.
 - ▶ Be aware of potential conditionalities that may impact participants' willingness to continue their involvement – as in the childcare example named above. In the case of questionnaires, this might entail the option of skipping questions or not having one question be a precondition for accessing another one.
 - ▶ Consider both the timing and type of participation format to make the activity more accessible to potential participants (e.g. physical vs. online events; events during holiday seasons; etc.).
 - ▶ Be aware of potential differences in knowledge, interest, resources, or capacity within your group of participants that might lead to tensions or power differences. It is essential to have a good facilitator that can ensure balance in the conversation, address bias, anticipate potential conflicts of interest, and ensure that the activity remains focused on the goals of the process. Make sure to create a friendly atmosphere.
 - ▶ Create clarity on and communicate transparently the roles and responsibilities of involved stakeholders. Ensure everyone has sufficient understanding of the process and their potential to contribute. This helps create trust in the process.
 - ▶ Plan enough time for each participatory activity to allow participants to think and provide feedback. However, also consider that too long an activity might be strenuous and hinder certain groups from participating.
 - ▶ Continuously adjust expectations and ambitions and manage resources proactively, anticipating bottlenecks, during all stages of the process.
 - ▶ An online tool can be helpful in collecting additional feedback. However, consider selecting a user-friendly tool that is accessible to everyone without creating additional efforts.
 - ▶ Try to make an ex-post reflection after each activity to share opinions and agree on core outputs. If this is not possible, try drafting a reporting template that includes input also by the moderators, to complete right after the activity. Reporting can be as important as the activity itself.
 - ▶ Provide clear guidelines on quality criteria for participatory processes and make sure that staff members responsible for the evaluation have enough experience with impact measurement.

1 Introduction

At the core of the PRO-Ethics project lie its “real-life experiments” – a total of 10 participatory pilots implemented in the context of the activities of research funding organizations (RFOs) in the project’s consortium. While 4 of these pilots were implemented at the beginning of the project and provided experiential inputs to the development of the first draft of the core output of PRO-Ethics – *D1.4 Ethics Framework 0.1 and Guidelines* – the present deliverable reports on the implementation of the second pilot phase, wherein the *Draft Ethics Framework* was tested and further refined. It gives insights into the pilots, two reflection formats organized between pilot partners, and two workshops held with research funding organizations external to the PRO-Ethics consortium, in the context of a collaboration with the TAFTIE network.

This report provides an overview of these activities and shares some of the lessons learned in the context of pilot phase II. Chapter 2 gives an overview of the employed methodology and collected materials. Chapter 3 outlines the overall processes of seven participatory pilots, including the frictions encountered, solutions found, and lessons learned by each research funding organization of the project consortium. This is followed in chapter 4 by a report on a reflection workshop held in November 2022 in the context of a general assembly meeting, and in chapter 5 on an evaluation workshop held in March 2023 in the context of the final cross-pilot learning workshop. Chapter 6 gives an overview of two external workshops held in collaboration with the TAFTIE network of national innovation agencies to collect additional insights and broaden the profile of the project. Chapter 7 summarizes the various lessons learned in the context of pilot phase II. Additional documentation of the process is shared in Annexes 1-3.

2 Methodology and Materials

This report provides insights into the engagement activities implemented in the context of PRO-Ethics' pilot phase II and details the efforts, experiences, and learnings of the project's RFO partners. To collect these experiences, several reporting formats were employed:

- ▶ ZSI developed a reporting template (see Annex 1) and instructed the implementing RFO partners to fill in a report for each of their activities. This template supported RFOs in conducting a structured reflection process and entailed general data on each activity, such as number and types of participants, goals and non-goals of the activity, recruitment process and engagement formats, and a general reflection on hurdles and results. Additionally, RFOs provided a summary of qualitative feedback gathered by their participants. In consultation with DBT, this reporting template was later amended to include a question on the experiences with the Ethics Framework and Guidelines each RFO made.
- ▶ Pilot implementing partners were asked in regular consortium calls (taking place every 6 weeks) to give a status update on their pilots. The minutes – and in some cases transcripts – were also included in outlining the pilot experiences.
- ▶ The pilot stories collected as part of T3.4 were also considered, as they provided important context and additional information enabling a better understanding of the pilots.
- ▶ All pilot partners were asked to provide a final pilot summary that included 1) the context of pilot activity; 2) the achievements of pilot activities; 3) the contributions made by participants; 4) the limitations of the pilot; and 5) the influence the pilot experiences have on further decision within the RFO. These summaries were provided between February and March 2023.
- ▶ Two interactive workshops were held in the context of physical meetings to collect further insights on the practical experiences of the RFO partners: A reflection workshop in November 2022 as part of the general assembly meeting, and an evaluation workshop in March 2023 as part of the third cross-pilot learning workshop.

In addition, two workshops were organized in cooperation with TAFTIE, where the *Ethics Framework* was presented and PRO-Ethics pilot experiences were shared, opening the floor to exchange and discussion with key stakeholders outside the project consortium.

These data were collected in collaboration with DBT and TUD. ZSI systematized them in accordance with the needs of the work package – focused on the experiences within the pilots as reported by the RFO partners. A first broad qualitative content analysis following Mayring¹ was undertaken by ZSI, coding both deductively, according to codes structured by the reporting template, and inductively as categories emerged from the data material. While these codes facilitated the writing of the present deliverable, as a report this document mainly summarizes the processes and findings of pilot phase II, presenting only some initial insights from this analysis, with more in-depth findings to follow in *D2.5 Paper Manuscript for Publication on Ethics in New Actor Constellations* and *D3.5 Synthesis Report on Pilot Experiences*.

The final pilot descriptions were shared with the RFO partners to review for accuracy and quality.

¹ Mayring, Philipp (2014). Qualitative content analysis: theoretical foundation, basic procedures and software solution. Klagenfurt, 2014. URN: <http://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:0168-ssaoar-395173>

3 Report on Phase II Pilots

In this chapter, an overview of each pilot implemented in phase II of PRO-Ethics is given, summarizing the processes and learnings by laying out each pilot's 1) goals; 2) recruitment formats, types of participants and compensation; 3) processes and participation formats; 4) frictions, solutions and lessons learned; and 5) efforts to achieve sustainability.

3.1 Pilot 5: Engaging Citizens in Project Evaluation and Implementation (VDI/VDE-IT)

As a research funding organization, VDI/VDE-IT works closely with the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research. The pilot of VDI/VDE-IT originated from this cooperation and was designed to accompany a funding call on technological solutions to support informal caregivers. The pilot set up a citizen advisory board (henceforth CAB), which participated in the proposal evaluation and selection of suitable projects. The members of the CAB are also involved as mentors during the implementation of the innovation projects at the time of writing of this report. The CAB consists of people who provide or have provided informal care to relatives, friends or acquaintances and are therefore regarded as lay experts in the field of informal care.

3.1.1 Goals

The main goal of the pilot was to involve (public) representatives of the target group in several key steps of the funding lifecycle, from proposal evaluation to research and development. The pilot thus enables informal caregivers to have a direct impact on the project selection and execution processes as well as the final product that is designed to support informal caregiving. In addition, their involvement would give CAB members an insight into the process of funding and developing technologies.

3.1.2 Recruitment, Types of Participants and Compensation

VDI/VDE-IT placed great emphasis on building a diverse panel of participants. The challenge here was to select a representative group of informal caregivers from different backgrounds and a wide range of care situations. The initial set of criteria was based on demographics (age, education, gender), location (city, small town, countryside, West/East Germany), and the personal caregiving-situation (person who to care for, intensity of care, reason for care). The next step was to contact multipliers such as caregiver organizations to pitch them the pilot concept and ask them for feedback, as well as suggestions for the best way to contact the target group. Most importantly, the organizations were asked how best to motivate informal caregivers to take part in the citizen panel. This was important as the target group could be considered 'vulnerable' due to factors such as the average socio-economic status of informal caregivers and the caregiver burden this group experiences. The meeting with multiplier organizations was very insightful in how to address these obstacles, and in addition, they helped disseminate the invitation for the online application. In the end, 40 meaningful applications were received by VDI/VDE-IT, from which 15 permanent CAB members and 4 reserve candidates were selected. Participants were selected in a way to achieve a balanced panel according to the criteria described above. Participants were compensated between 60€ and 120€ for their participation in meetings and activities, as well as up to 100€ for care expenses. While most activities took place online, travel costs for physical meetings were also reimbursed.

3.1.3 Process and Participation Formats

The CAB met for the first time online on 24. August 2021, in a meeting that also included representatives of the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research as well as members of VDI/VDE-IT of whom some represented the PRO-Ethics team. The care attorney for the federal government also showed great

interest in the project and sent a welcoming address per video. In this **kick-off meeting**, the members of the CAB got to know each other and learned about the goals and processes of the pilot. In addition, it provided the opportunity to exchange experiences and discuss the needs specific to participants' situation as informal caregivers as well as their expectations regarding the pilot. Following this meeting, a **chat group for CAB members** was created on the messaging app Signal to encourage exchange and community building outside the context of CAB meetings.

On 16. and 17. September 2021, CAB members received an online **briefing on the proposal evaluation and selection process** that VDI/VDE-IT uses to decide which projects should receive funding, offering a shortened and simplified version of the rating criteria. In addition, project applicants had been required to provide a summary of the proposal in accessible language, which the CAB members received as a basis for their evaluation. While CAB members were assigned specific proposals, with each proposal being rated by two people, pilot participants received access to all proposals in full, including both the simplified and the more comprehensive scientific version. After the meeting, the **board members individually rated project drafts online from home**, having access to both scientific and simplified versions of the proposals.

On 12. October 2021, an online **selection session** for the CAB was conducted, where the ratings for each proposal were discussed and the board members made a selection of drafts that the panel would recommend for funding. The CAB also elected two spokespeople to represent it in the scientific board meeting where the final funding decision would be made. On 18. and 19. November 2021, the **final selection session** took place online. The scientific panel consisting of scientists and care experts met with the chosen representatives of the CAB to determine the conclusive selection of project proposals. On 3. December 2021, the CAB met for a **joint reflection** of past activities and presentation of the projects selected in November. Furthermore, each CAB member was asked to select a project to mentor during the upcoming research phase. The meeting included a survey on workload, duration of appointments, content of appointments, communication, overall content, and fulfilment of expectations.

During an online networking meeting on 15. and 16. March 2022, the **CAB and the funded projects met for the first time**. In this session, project managers and CAB members got acquainted with one another, and each project was given time for an introduction. The meeting also provided space for exchange, discussion, and questions. Throughout 2022, CAB members took part in a variety of activities, starting with the kick-off meetings of the projects they are mentoring and followed by two practical "hands-on" meetings through which they **directly worked with the projects on their ideas, concepts and proceedings**. In addition, two networking events between all projects were organized by VDI/VDE-IT.

Finally, on 7. March 2023, a **first in-person meeting of the CAB** was organized by VDI/VDE-IT, with representatives from the Ministry of Education and Research also present. This meeting was dedicated to **reflecting the process so far**, including both project selection and mentoring, and how the CAB members felt about the pilot at that point in time.

3.1.4 Frictions, Solutions and Lessons Learned

The greatest friction in the process stemmed from the **varying degree to which CAB members were able to contribute time, resources and knowledge**. This was juxtaposed to the need to create a fair process where everyone's opinion had equal value. The projects that the CAB was assessing had submitted short and simplified versions of their application in order to reduce the burden on the CAB. However, while some CAB members stuck with reading the simplified versions of the four proposals assigned to each of them, others read all proposals in their entirety. This in turn led to considerable knowledge imbalances when it came to discussing the evaluations in the group, which were further exacerbated by the different backgrounds of CAB members. As the panel was set up to be intentionally

diverse, some participants could draw on their expertise in IT or professional care, which allowed them to speak with more confidence or underpin their arguments with additional information to support their positions. Ensuring that all members felt valued and that decisions were taken in a fair manner presented a challenge, which fell on the session facilitators to enable. In a reflection report, VDI/VDE-IT staff stated that it was a challenge not to restrict the more engaged CAB members and allow some flexibility in how participants get involved, while simultaneously avoiding the (power) imbalances that occurred in the process. Overall, this raised the question within the VDI/VDE-IT team how boundaries between flexibility and rigidity should be drawn to ensure balance and fairness within a participatory process. **A lesson drawn from this experience is to create clarity on the extent and structure of participant involvement beforehand and to reflect on how to approach different levels of contributions and motivation within a group of participants.**

Regarding the mentoring process for funded projects, similar issues arose with regards to CAB members' capacity to contribute. On the one hand, some members wanted to be involved in all steps and contribute their professional expertise, even going so far as to demand regular reports from the project owners which was not a planned interaction mode in the mentoring process. On the other hand, some CAB members stated they were overwhelmed just with the task as it was set by VDI/VDE-IT. Thus, one of the challenges as described by VDI/VDE-IT lay in moderating the engagement of some members without dampening their motivation, and thus mitigate existing divisions within the panel brought forth by various gaps in available resources, such as time, money, motivation and education. **Here, a balance needs to be found where the efforts of more engaged members can be valued and utilized, while less engaged members or those with fewer resources are not overwhelmed by the complexity of the process or the workload.**

Another important lesson from the pilot is to **set and communicate processes, roles and responsibilities transparently**. CAB members feedback on their involvement with the projects was mixed, as some reported a smooth experience, while others found that their role was unclear or they felt that their inputs were not valued to the extent that they would expect. In other projects, problems arose because CAB members were drawing on their professional expertise in IT, engineering or research and gave input on aspects of the projects they mentored beyond their expertise as informal caregivers. This led to some heated discussions and a need to (re-)negotiate the role of the mentor in situ. A few times, VDI/VDE-IT had to step in to mediate between the board members and project. In response to these frictions, VDI/VDE-IT organized separate meetings, one with all the projects and another one with CAB members only, to discuss experiences and decide on the process moving forward. Again, the lesson here is that it would have been **helpful to have more clarity on the scope and the limits of the involvement of the CAB in the innovation process**, both for the projects as well as for the CAB. At the same time, it needs to be considered that guidelines and tighter monitoring come at the expense of flexibility for projects and mentors to design the process as it best suits them.

Managing the CAB members' expectation of project outcomes and familiarizing them with the **scientific procedures** proved to be another challenge of expectation management. Overall, informal caregivers are a group that is under great and constant mental and physical strain due to their situation. Their motivation to participate in helping in improving the situation of informal caregivers is therefore exceptionally high, while they are at the same time hoping for immediate results. This sometimes collides with the logic of research projects of more extensive literature work and cautious development of problem solutions. Here, it was necessary to explain and discuss the logic of scientific projects and the foreseen exploitation of outcomes that are not meant to result in a finalized, market-ready product.

A final, related set of challenges arose on the issue of **barriers to participation**. CAB members were compensated for their participation in activities, and received additional reimbursement for care

expenses arising in the process. However, due to usual administrative procedures, transfer of these payments sometimes took longer than some members of the CAB would have expected and preferred. This proved burdensome for the most socio-economically vulnerable members. Similarly, not all participants were able to pay for travel expenses incurred in the fulfilment of their responsibilities in advance, to be reimbursed after the event. Here, the pilot team took care to find a solution to work around this administrative procedure. This was further exacerbated as sometimes, the projects planned meetings far from where their assigned mentors lived. While travel costs, accommodation and a fixed allowance for participation and care could be compensated by VDI/VDE-IT, travelling time itself was not accounted for. Furthermore, the travelling time itself was too long for some CAB members. This could partially be solved by organizing hybrid meetings, although this was seen as an imperfect solution, with many board members expressing their desire for in-person meetings. A future solution could be to coordinate meetings to be in a more central location.

3.1.5 Sustainability

The pilot implemented by VDI/VDE-IT received support by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research and will continue beyond the runtime of PRO-Ethics. Due to the specificities of the pilot – including citizens not only in proposal evaluation but also as mentors in the implementation of innovation projects – it entails vast learning potential in a so far underserved field. These learnings are valuable beyond the concrete organizational context of VDI/VDE-IT, especially since the German R&I ecosystem is currently undergoing relevant structural adaptations. For instance, the newly established Society for Transdisciplinary and Participatory Research² and the Alliance of Science Organisations on Citizen Participation in Research³ may benefit from building on the insights and activities of VDI/VDE-IT.

VDI/VDE-IT is planning an embedding event with Ministry representatives to establish clear processes for potential future participatory actions in the context of the organization's activities. Furthermore, the RFO is considering the implementation of an additional embedding event that includes a wider net of stakeholders and disseminating the Ethics Framework among a wider circle of interested actors in the German R&I ecosystem.

3.2 Pilot 6: Citizen Participation Learning Hub (RCN)

RCN is a Norwegian government agency funding both basic and applied research and innovation. The RCN pilot has been carried out in close cooperation with RCL, which fulfils a similar role funding R&D in Lithuania. The *Involve Hub* developed in the context of RCN's second pilot builds on former and ongoing experiences with participatory activities at RCN, including some carried out in collaboration with RCL. While these were carried out without a special focus on research ethics or research integrity, the *Involve Hub* entails a network of key stakeholders to share knowledge, discuss challenges and identify solutions related to ethical participation in R&I. The Hub was organized in three gatherings during the period August 2022 to January 2023, as well as two preliminary integrating workshops prior to the Hub-gatherings (on 28. January and 27. April).

3.2.1 Goals

The *Involve Hub* was developed as a community of practice hub for mutual exchange on various aspects and ethical dilemmas of citizens participation in scientific knowledge production. Thematically, these activities 1) addressed potential ethical challenges of citizen involvement in research, 2) invited inputs

² See <https://www.td-academy.org/en/tdacademy/professional-society/>

³ See <https://www.allianz-der-wissenschaftsorganisationen.de/en/topics-statements/citizen-participation-in-research/>

for developing the Ethics Framework, and 3) collected feedback on how the Research Council can work better with regards to ethical citizen involvement.

3.2.2 Recruitment, Types of Participants and Compensation

The target group of the Involve Hub gatherings were project managers and participants in projects with citizen involvement funded by the Research Council (and EU), within health care research, climate and environmental research and research on issues related to challenged youth. This included both researchers, municipal/regional/national institutions, key national actors such as research ethics committees, The Norwegian Association of Local and Regional Authorities (KS) and Innovation Norway, as well as non-profit organizations in the field.

Considering that this community is very busy in their work-related activities, having them engaged in several activities of the Involve Hub was a challenge for the RCN staff, making recruitment somewhat challenging. As a first step, RCN and RCL completed a mapping of the ecosystem to identify stakeholders while keeping in mind diversity among participants concerning gender, geography, research field, and organization/sector. In the mapping process, RCN gathered knowledge and contacts from various staff members related to existing projects and project participants, networks, and relations established through participation in different events and forums.

Secondly, participants were invited via e-mail, emphasizing the benefits of their participation such as knowledge sharing, establishment of new contacts, and valorization of their contribution through the development of RCN's instruments for user participation in R&I, as well as contribution towards the development of the Ethics Framework.

3.2.3 Process and Participation Formats

As part of the Involve Hub, RCN organized three online gatherings taking place between August 2022 to January 2023 and engaging a relatively stable group of participants: The first workshop kicked off the process with a focus on **ethical challenges when citizens are involved in research**. It included an expert introduction as well as input from three researchers with experience in citizen involvement, each followed by a Q&A. In the end, some time was left for an open discussion between the 20 participants of the gathering. In the course of the workshop, the various inputs – prepared and spontaneous – highlighted important issues and reflections on the ethics of citizen participation.

The second workshop with 17 participants built on the learnings of the first event, regarding both the contents and the format, leaving more time for discussion. It entailed a presentation on the Ethics Framework by the primary author of the first draft, PRO-Ethics colleague Kalli Giannelos of Sciences Po, who shared the background, goals and content of the guidelines. This was followed by an input by RCN pilot lead Anila Nauni, on how the Practical Guidelines were interpreted in the Norwegian context. RCN received constructive and concrete feedback on the Ethics Framework. One of the comments emphasized the value of the Framework beyond R&I projects and processes, while another underlined the importance of giving guidance on the inclusion of vulnerable groups and securing their representation, as well as the value of compensation of participants.

The third workshop focused on RCN's work on ethics and citizen involvement. RCN colleagues working on research ethics held a presentation about the organization's role and about its future plans in this field. These inputs also laid out how the Ethics Framework will be integrated in RCN's work on ethics. Two participants were asked to prepare reflections and suggestions on how RCN can improve its work in this field. RCN received some very concrete and useful input and suggestions from the participants, which will be considered for further work at the Research Council. These include:

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- ▶ Consider having a budget to compensate citizens/users participating in research and innovation projects.
 - ▶ Where relevant, the calls should encourage applicants to actively consider participation from citizens/users.
 - ▶ RCN calls should be clear on how the organization evaluates proposals that consider participation from citizens/users. What are the evaluation criteria?
 - ▶ Make a clear distinction between user involvement and citizen science.

Another useful contribution from the perspective of the national research ethics committees pertained to the challenges facing this work and suggested that there might be a need for clearer roles and responsibility when it comes to ethics in research.

In parallel to these Hub meetings, RCN tried to establish an online platform to develop and strengthen the community of practice beyond the three gatherings. Unfortunately, this mobilization did not gain lasting momentum and the server was finally shut down in May 2023.

RCN implemented the pilot in collaboration with RCL, who were involved when RCN initially planned the concept of the hub and gatherings, and in a reflection meeting after the first two gatherings, where the experiences of the pilot were discussed. The Hub gatherings themselves were held mostly in Norwegian.

3.2.4 Frictions, Solutions and Lessons Learned

The main achievements of pilot activities are the knowledge exchange between the participants and the broadening of the perspectives of the involved stakeholders as they contributed with their expertise. The Hub activity created a systemic perspective on the changes needed to embark on the mandate on ethics of involvement. The contributions of participants were mainly through the Hub gathering realized as online interactions. After the end of each online event, the participants were invited to provide further feedback through an online platform. As part of this secondary online exchange, participants had the chance to share their inputs on three topics: 1) What are the most important ethical challenges you have come across in processes or projects with user involvement; 2) Provide input to the Draft Ethical Framework developed by PRO-Ethics; and 3.) What kind of support would you wish for, when planning and/or implementing processes/projects with user involvement, when it comes to ethical challenges?. As discussed above, this online format could not be sustainably established, which was at least in part due to technical difficulties that only made the infrastructure available towards the very end of the process. Furthermore, the user interface was not accessible enough for the users. Thus, continuous engagement could no longer be supported via the direct interactions of iterative Hub gatherings. This might have been further exacerbated by lack of time on the side of participants and missing incentives for repeated communication through the platform. In the end, only a small percentage of participants used the tool to provide additional feedback.

While at least one of the Hub gatherings was intended to be held in person, there were not enough registrations beforehand to warrant this effort, which led RCN to hold the final workshop online as well. Thus, choosing the right engagement format(s) and being willing to adapt are important lessons from this process. Furthermore, RCN emphasized the importance of a good moderator in keeping a balance between different participants' interactions and providing summaries of what was being said to make sure everyone understood and registered the others' inputs. Finally timing was an issue also on this smaller scale, as RCN found there wasn't sufficient time to discuss following the speaker inputs, especially in the first workshop. This also led to some attendees acting more as passive observers than active participants.

3.2.5 Sustainability

A general assessment of the Involve Hub events displays overall positive feedback from all participants related to the topic of ethical participation and their interest in providing feedback. While RCN is currently considering how to keep the Hub active after the third event, several of the participants have shared that they are interested in participating in future activities related to ethics and stakeholder involvement. Positive feedback from participants is a supporting factor for continuing with participatory approaches to enhance credibility and trust. RCN is also considering the adoption of the Ethics Framework as the guiding document for planning, designing and implementing future participatory activities at different stages of the R&I process.

3.3 Pilot 7: Citizen Participation in Call Topic Definition (FFG)

FFG is the Austrian national funding agency for applied and industrial research and innovation and manages funding mostly provided by different ministries and other public institutions. For several years, the FFG R&I funding programs *benefit* and *AAL* have focused on combining pressing issues of demographic change with the development of useful ICT-based solutions. The programs are now evolving into a new funding topic called “Digital Solutions for People and Society”. Under the umbrella of this new theme, it is the aim of the FFG pilot to explore relevant subtopics that combine health topics, climate change and demographic change, while also taking into consideration the possibilities that information and communication technologies offer. As part of this pilot, FFG involves citizens in the definition of call topics through a four-step process: First, FFG team members conducted expert interviews to inform the approach FFG was taking. This was followed by a validation workshop with a wider group of stakeholders to deepen and validate the information received in the expert interviews. In the third phase, an online survey was shared through various channels with potentially interested citizens to collect their input and experiences with regard to the pilot topic. Finally, another validation workshop is planned to validate specific aspects of the survey, which has not been carried out and documented by the time of writing this report.

3.3.1 Goals

The overall goal of the pilot was to elaborate topics for a funding call based on the input of experts and, most importantly, citizens in the broadest sense. The objective was to develop the topics of a call for research, development and innovation projects that are addressing what matters most to citizens. Since FFG does not usually perform broader citizen engagement processes when defining call topics, this was a new experience for the team.

The separate activities had individual goals. The expert interviews in the beginning were used to get a deeper understanding of the topic. The first validation workshop had the goal to deepen and validate information from the expert interviews and to find out more about the interrelation between climate change, health, and technology so that the lives of citizens could be improved effectively. The expert interviews and first validation workshop built the base to design the online questionnaire that was subsequently made available online for self-selected citizens participation. This questionnaire was the key activity, collecting comments, preferences, and ideas from citizens. A first call for proposals has been launched based on these three steps. FFG aims to conduct another validation workshop with the results from the survey and launch a second call at the end of 2023.

3.3.2 Recruitment, Types of Participants and Compensation

For the expert interview phase, FFG started with well-known experts in the field and employed a snowballing method to identify further interview partners. Starting from well-known experts in the field, through recommendations a total of thirteen semi-structured interviews with experts, including

practitioners, could be conducted in the end. The interview partners were also intended as multipliers for engaging citizens, which was however not successful. The first validation workshop was organized as part of the IMAGINE conference hosted yearly in collaboration between the Federal Ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology (BMK) and the FFG in Vienna. The conference, which is usually well-attended, has a specific focus on digital technologies and targets both industry and research performing institutions. The pilot event was advertised through FFG channels and at the conference itself. Fourteen participants attended the workshop, representing beneficiaries of funded projects, end users and policymakers.

The following citizen survey was set up as an online questionnaire to reach a high number of people as efficiently as possible. Participation was largely based on self-selection, with FFG promoting the survey through external and internal newsletters, as well as professional and private networks. FFG contacted several multiplier organizations to share the survey, but this did not yield the desired result. Nevertheless, response rates were satisfactory, with 123 valid (i.e. complete) responses out of around 180. The survey was open from the end of June until mid-August 2022. FFG also collected demographic data through the questionnaire and found significant self-selection bias in their sample, which skewed female, middle-aged, and towards people with higher levels of education.

There was no compensation for participation in any of the pilot activities.

3.3.3 Process and Participation Formats

The pilot team at FFG first needed to secure budget and commitment and find a suitable funding scheme for this new participatory process. To this end, ministry partners needed to be onboarded throughout 2021. FFG designed and then started implementing a multi-step process to investigate relevant dimensions of climate change, health, and demographic change, taking also into consideration the role technologies might play as an enabler.

A **first exploration phase** included selected stakeholders and experts through **13 semi-structured interviews** in early 2022. Insights gained there were analyzed in May and June 2022.

In June 2022, at the **validation workshop** the results and insights from the interviews were discussed and the participants contributed their expertise on the nexus of climate change, health and technology. The main activity of the workshop was a 'brainwalk' where participants walked between four stations and discussed with the host of that station on a specific topic. The hosts were experts from FFG as well as thematically relevant cooperation partners, a care institution, the AAL Austria⁴ platform and the ministry funding the planned calls. At the end of the activity, the hosts summarized the discussions at their station.

Based on the inputs collected in the first two steps, a **questionnaire** was developed, consisting of both closed and open questions, and aimed at collecting inputs on the experiences and expectations of citizens regarding the interrelation between climate change, health, and RDI funding projects. The survey focused on finding out important issues for citizens, and their thematically relevant experiences. To reach a high number of people as efficiently as possible, the survey was set up and disseminated in an online format. While FFG initially explored the option of using the identified IT-tool CONSUL for this activity, the software proved too limited to set up the questionnaire as intended. Consequently, a dedicated survey tool was employed, with the survey being open from the end of June until mid-August 2022. The activity led to abundant and rich responses from participants with a total of 123 completed surveys. While the FFG designed the survey to be as short, easy and accessible as possible, to their

⁴ A platform for innovations for intelligent assistance for everyday life

surprise the open questions yielded much more input than expected. This allowed FFG to gain deeper insights and new ideas for the funding call.

In December 2022, FFG **launched the first funding call based on the results of the different stages of the process**. A second call is planned to follow at the end of 2023. In addition, FFG plans to hold a second validation workshop to deepen insight into selected thematically relevant aspects. The results from all pilot activities will also be analyzed to feed into a **study** the FFG is developing that will report on the pilot and summarize the received input.

3.3.4 Frictions, Solutions and Lessons Learned

FFG experienced the biggest challenges with the **recruitment of participants** for the validation workshop and the citizen survey. While the validation workshop was advertised through FFG channels before the conference, on-site visibility was limited and the number of participants (14) remained well below the desired number. The FFG team concluded from this experience that it is important to always ensure on-site visibility when cooperating with external events. For the citizen survey, FFG had originally planned to employ the help of multiplier organizations to reach the desired target group. However, even though several organizations initially showed interest in supporting the project, this never materialized. FFG identified as reasons for this privacy concerns and missing buy-in from higher levels in the hierarchy, limited time and resources at these organizations, but also potential rivalry regarding the engagement of available citizens. In turn, it would need **more time and effort to establish more solid, trustful collaborations with such stakeholders in the future**. To reach the intended target group, FFG instead used its own communication, such as the newsletter and social media channels, preexisting collaboration channels and private networks. One of the lessons learned from this process is **the importance of being flexible and open to try different approaches**. In the end, through the mix of communication channels, FFG received a sufficient number of responses.

FFG also expressed some insecurities regarding the right approach to participatory processes. The expert interviews allowed the FFG team to gain valuable insights that were validated and expanded in the validation workshop, which was perceived as a positive experience. However, there were some uncertainties about the sufficient number of participants in the workshop and respondents in the survey. A clear guideline on quality criteria for participatory processes in the sense of minimum requirements would be helpful in the future.

The self-selection of participants for the validation workshop and the citizen survey meant that there was a strong bias in participants towards middle-aged women with higher education. While this fact raised questions regarding representativeness of the sample and overall inclusivity of the participatory process, it also meant that participants were highly motivated and responses had a high rate of answering open questions comprehensively. FFG had been advised in discussions with potential multipliers and the consortium to keep the questionnaire very simple and ask mainly closed questions. However, presumably due to the make-up of the participant group, many survey respondents provided rich inputs and important considerations via the open questions. While this resulted in a lot more unexpected effort to analyze the responses, it was counted as a success for the process and gave valuable insights for the call definition.

Overall, FFG identified a number of learnings for their own processes:

- ▶ Be flexible: If the chosen approach does not work out, change it and try a different approach.
- ▶ Don't set expectations too high: E.g. in terms of representativeness of the involved group of citizens).

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- ▶ Minimize participation barriers: E.g. allow respondents to skip questions in a questionnaire and do not make the answer to one question a precondition for accessing the next question; put the questions related to demographic data at the end of the questionnaire.
 - ▶ Surprises are possible: E.g. in a very high response rate to open questions.
 - ▶ Think well about the timing of the launch of a survey: Launching a questionnaire on climate change and health in the summer seemed to be good timing.
 - ▶ An online tool is helpful to reaching out to people without requiring much time resources.

3.3.5 Sustainability

In December 2022, the first call based on the outcomes and insights of the participatory process was launched. FFG plans to launch a second call later in the year 2023. To secure the budget for either call launched on the basis of a participatory process, it was important to get the partner from the funding ministry on board. Hence, the general fit of the broad topic was decided in advance in conversation with the ministry to fit its overall strategy, to be then narrowed down within the pilot process. However, if the conditions (and the ministry's strategy) change then FFG might find itself with less funding than desired for the topics arising from the participatory process.

In the second half of 2023, FFG is planning to hold a workshop with the ministry to determine whether it is worthwhile to continue with citizen involvement and how the approach could be used for other programs, too. This will be followed by a second event organized in collaboration with ZSI, the LBG OIS Centre, and the Austrian platform for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation fteval. This event aims at ensuring the visibility of the Ethics Framework and Guidelines in the Austrian R&I ecosystem.

3.4 Pilot 8: Citizen Participation in Thematic Definition of Program Calls (Innoviris)

Innoviris is a public organization that funds and supports research and innovation in the Brussels Capital Region (BCR) and (co-)finances R&I projects in companies, research centers, and the non-profit and public sector. The pilot aimed to find a suitable design and method for engaging a broad cut of the population living in the Brussel Capital Region and identify challenges in the BCR that should be addressed through funding by Innoviris, via its policy-oriented research program Prospective Research. As a first step, the team at Innoviris conducted desk research to identify concrete challenges from the Regional Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisations⁵ (RIS3), which is distilled from political plans, megatrends, data analyses, and so on. The base layer for call topics at Innoviris is always the list of challenges identified through the participative RIS3 strategy. This was followed by a consultation with regional public actors and centers of expertise with knowledge on regional challenges, implemented through a semi-directive online questionnaire collecting inputs on the challenges identified through the desk research. Based on this, Innoviris developed and conducted an open online survey with residents of the BCR. Finally, two citizen ateliers were organized in person, where residents of the Brussels area discussed different urban challenges with experts and among themselves.

3.4.1 Goals

The pilot by Innoviris had two main goals: 1) To conduct a single and more comprehensive consultation to identify important urban challenges for future regional policies that should be addressed by researchers with direct feedback from individual citizens; and 2) To use the pilot to develop a set of guidelines for a more systematic and global approach for citizen participation in processes of agenda setting and scientific knowledge production. In addition, each activity also had individual goals. With the

⁵ See <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/> and https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/documents/portlet_file_entry/20125/RIS3+Guide.pdf/19fa7820-9522-3a52-fb81-6cb9115b6b9f

consultation of regional actors, Innoviris wanted to check, refine and focus current challenges as they were identified from documents such as RIS3. The online survey that presented citizens with five challenges identified in the previous activities provided a chance to add new and emerging challenges. For the citizen panel, which met in person twice, the goal was to allow a diverse audience to share opinions and knowledge, thus initiating a public dialogue between citizens, representatives of different RRI programs and experts.

3.4.2 Recruitment, Types of Participants and Compensation

For the online consultation of regional actors, Innoviris approached 19 public actors and centres of expertise in their network via a semi-directive questionnaire. Of these, 6 sent responses with suggestions for key research themes linked to local challenges. From these, and based on desk research and input from internal experts, an online survey for residents of the BCR was developed, which were approached through a snowball method. The link to the survey was sent to local multipliers with the request to diffuse the invitation via their proper networks. In total, 42 contacts from as many public and private centers of expertise in urban challenges were targeted. The centers of expertise were divided into 6 groups, representing the regional strategic priorities (RIS3): 1) climate and energy, 2) resource optimization, 3) mobility, 4) nutrition, 5) health, and 6) inclusive and participatory society. As a result of their efforts, Innoviris received 59 valid responses to the online survey.

To recruit participants for the citizen ateliers, Innoviris was helped by an external provider. First a communication campaign was launched on social media with a link to a subscription form including questions on socio-demographic data (needed for the sampling of citizens in the subsequent phase). Unfortunately, the recruitment campaign had to be aborted after a few days following the identification, by political representatives, of politically sensitive information - statements around the various social issues were used on social media to draw attention. This resulted in only 11 citizens subscribing through this channel. Second, via interviewers in the streets, groups less represented in the online sphere were targeted, such as people with limited access to digital tools, people in hard-to-reach cultural and socioeconomic spheres. Four interviewers working in two pairs recruited 103 participants between 13 and 22 June 2022, resulting in a total of 114 registrations via the subscription form. From these, a random sample of 21 citizens by socio-demographic criteria was drawn using the Open Source Software "StratifySelect", generating a representative panel that captures the diversity of the population of the BCR. The selection of the 21 citizens intended to participate in the citizen atelier workshops was based on the following criteria:

- ▶ Gender: Generally a mix of about 50/50, or proportionally to the composition of the Brussels population.
- ▶ Age distribution, in proportion to the composition of the Brussels population for groups over 18 years old: 18-24 years; 25-34 years old; 35-44 years old; 45-54 years old; 55-64 years old; 65+ years.
- ▶ Socio-economic origins in proportion to the composition of the Brussels population, including level of education and occupation.
- ▶ A geographical distribution according to the six police zones.

After the sample was drawn, each participant was contacted individually to confirm their attendance of the workshops. Those who were no longer available or did not want to participate were replaced by people with the most similar profile to maintain the highest possible degree of representation. However, as many participants declined the invitation, in the end many of the people in the sample had to be contacted personally.

While the aim was to recruit a representative sample of inhabitants of the BCR, the citizens who actually participated in the survey and the citizen panel were quite representative. A light bias existed towards a higher than average socio-economic and educational background. The gender balance was 60/40, but older people (>55 years) and people with only primary education levels were not included. Participants received €30 in compensation for participating in the citizen panel's two meetings. In addition, catering was provided on both evenings.

3.4.3 Process and Participation Formats

The pilot team at Innoviris consisted of an internal task force composed of the program manager, internal advisors, team leaders and policy and monitoring experts. To prepare for the pilot, this team conducted desk research to identify the challenges from local and regional documents, such as RIS3 or other regional development strategies. This was followed by a **consultation of regional public actors and centers of expertise** with knowledge on regional challenges. Nineteen actors within the Innoviris network were approached via a semi-directive online questionnaire. Six questionnaires were returned with suggestions for key research themes linked to local challenges framed within the region's smart specialization domains.

Building on these inputs, the task force developed an **online survey for citizens of the Brussels Capital Region** using the citizen participation tool CONSUL to engage citizens in topic prioritization throughout June 2022. Innoviris chose to limit this exploration to the five most important challenges identified by the expert consultation, which were presented on the platform with a short description in English, Dutch and French:

- ▶ **Social inequality and poverty – climate change as an accelerator:** The challenge of social inequality and specifically poverty that typifies Brussels is magnified in a number of themes. Climate change, for instance, usually hits the least affluent population the hardest, and energy poverty is a growing problem. How to avoid that climate change divides society?
- ▶ **Polarisation of society:** In our regional safety survey, 7 out of 10 residents of Brussels consider polarisation to be an important issue. Living together and understanding each other is key to a liveable city environment but seems to be challenging. Which policies could help to overcome this challenge?
- ▶ **The real estate market – available and affordable space:** Citizens, as well as public bodies, are finding it increasingly difficult to find affordable and qualitative space in the Region. Are we going to sacrifice our parks to build schools and social housing? How do we guarantee quality and affordable housing in the territory and avoid a flight beyond the Region's borders?
- ▶ **Well-being in a security society:** Senses of fear and anxiety are on the rise, public discourses report a state of emergency and situations are coded by alert levels yellow, orange, red. We seem to want more security in a world perceived as increasingly threatening. But does this quest for security contribute to the wellbeing of Brussels and its inhabitants, and on what levels?
- ▶ **Media and society:** Which media are beneficial to which societies? Advertising in the city is everywhere, more dependent and independent media compete for citizens' attention, with business and politics intertwining. How to develop a critical mind in this society, as a Brussels citizen? Should we move towards media sobriety?

From these, participants were asked to choose the most important challenge facing the region in the next 20 years. Through an open question, respondents could also name an additional challenge not represented above. Finally, demographic data was also gathered, while respondents were given the option of sharing their contact details for follow-up activities.

Building on the inputs provided by 59 survey participants, Innoviris implemented two **citizen ateliers**, which met twice for 3-4 hours each on the evenings of 30. June and 6. July 2022. The first workshop was designed as a **reverse science café**. Of 23 confirmed participants, only 10 attended. Citizens were

split into different thematic working groups to discuss subthemes with which citizens have experience and affinity in their daily life. Each topic was supported by an expert from Innoviris. The goal of this workshop was to allow a diverse audience to share their opinions and knowledge, thus initiating a public dialogue involving citizens and representatives of different RRI programs or policy processes. The group discussions result in recommendations briefly summarized in writing. The second citizen atelier was designed as a **scenario workshop**, which was intended as a direct follow-up activity to the previous meeting. While the same participants were invited once more, only 3 people took part in this second iteration. The scenario at the center of the activity was intended as a first scoping of a potential future call. It was developed by Innoviris prior to the meeting, based on the outcome of the reverse science café. This scenario was critically discussed by the participants from different backgrounds on the basis of their own experiences. While participation in these activities was disappointing, the outcome of these workshops helped Innoviris redefine the focus of the call and develop relevant research questions.

3.4.4 Frictions, Solutions and Lessons Learned

Innoviris experienced significant challenges in the implementation of its pilot, many of which are structural in nature and pertain to the specificities of the BCR. Brussels is a majority-minority city, home to people from over 170 different nationalities with only 25,7% of its population having a Belgian background. This in turn leads to a profound cultural and linguistic diversity among the residents of the area, which is further exacerbated by pervasive socio-economic factors. One in three residents of the BCR lives below the poverty line and there is a considerable gap between rich and poor. Thus, while Innoviris went to great lengths to involve a broad spectrum of the population via representative sampling, **severe restraints in time and funding meant the task force had little leeway to reflect on and adjust its approach.**

While Innoviris for instance identified relevant multiplier organizations with access to the intended target groups, they did not seem to diffuse the link to the online survey as requested. This might be because June in general is a busy time of the year and there are lots of participation initiatives going on simultaneously. At the same time, due to call deadlines and internal processes Innoviris was not able to adjust their own timeline and set activities after the summer break. As a consequence, the respondents of the online survey were over 95% higher educated, thus not at all representative of the Brussels Capital Region. Recruitment for the citizen panel was even more difficult. While Innoviris had previously been successful with online recruitment approaches, the social media campaign for the PRO-Ethics pilot had to be taken offline after only a few days because some of the contents of the campaign (namely the statements) were deemed too sensitive in the current political climate. This meant the task force had to reorganize the recruitment campaign on extremely short notice. To maximize the chances of success, Innoviris engaged a professional participant recruitment company, which tried to reach participants via street recruitment. Here, however, it became apparent that certain (age) groups were less likely to respond to a street survey, making it extremely difficult to reach citizens over the age of 45 for instance. In general, Innoviris had the impression participants recruited on the street were less intrinsically motivated (something that has been confirmed in other recruitment campaigns by the recruitment company) and thus more likely to discontinue their involvement than those citizens recruited through other methods, in particular the online campaign. From the 114 people recruited in total, it has required a lot of personal effort (telephone calls, text messages etc.) to achieve a total of 23 individuals who were willing to confirm their participation in the citizen ateliers at all. Of these, only 10 attended the first citizen panel workshop and only three attended the second, even though a text message reminder was sent to all participants the morning of the atelier. The Innoviris team assumes that on top of the recruitment methodology, timing again played a role in this disinterest, as June and July are busy months, especially for people with children. Moreover, other regional citizen participation campaigns were active simultaneously with the Innoviris campaign, which might point towards the importance of

coordinated action of citizen participation actions. Even though compensation was offered, most of the confirmed participants did not attend. For Innoviris, a possible mitigation strategy could be to **offer childcare options** in addition to compensation, to make it easier for parents to attend. **Limiting the needed involvement** by organizing only one workshop and/or shortening the timeframe of the event might also be helpful. Finally, **involving key stakeholders such as politicians and other decision-makers from the very beginning** and maybe even **seek contractual agreements with all parties, especially political ones, detailing the plans from the beginning in order to avoid similar roadblocks.**

The final barrier to participation that has been especially relevant to the Innoviris pilot are language issues. As Brussels is a multicultural and diverse region, not everyone is able to speak even one of the three official languages. However, due to budget and time constraints, the survey was only published in Dutch, French and English, while recruitment for the citizen panel was only in Dutch and French. This excluded a big part of the population of the BCR while it may have deterred others who feel less secure or fluent in any of these languages. Overall, the experiences made in the implementation of the pilot point towards a need of adjusting the expectations implementers have towards a process to the available time, budget and expertise they have at their disposal. Trying to achieve a representative sample – as the Brussels Parliament does – without having the means to reproduce their process (i.e. employing the national register and building on existing infrastructures) might have been overly ambitious.

3.4.5 Sustainability

Innoviris is currently involved in the strategic development of a center of expertise on citizen engagement at the regional level. As part of this, the RFO further plans an embedding event aimed at relevant regional stakeholders on all levels to institutionalize expertise on participatory approaches in RDI and anchor the Ethics Framework and Guidelines as a resource for all R&I actors in the Brussels Capital Region.

3.5 Pilot 9: Citizen Participation in the National R&D Strategy 2021-2027 (UEFISCDI)

UEFISCDI is a national Romanian research funding agency that has contributed to the development of the National Research, Innovation and Smart Specialisation Strategy 2022-2027. In the context of the pilot activities, UEFISCDI decided to employ a participatory approach to refine the 2022-2027 Romanian National Agenda for Research by engaging citizens in validating and enriching the proposed thematic priorities. The Strategic Research Agenda is a list of societal challenges and leading questions elaborated through a lengthy process with experts and public bodies. The two interactive workshops implemented by UEFISCDI were thus aimed at aligning the outputs experts and public authorities with the needs and experiences of citizens.

3.5.1 Goals

The goal of these pilots was to test if such an ambitious endeavor, namely involving citizens in the development of national, strategic documents and instruments, was possible, especially considering that these kinds of initiatives are usually the prerogatives of authorities and experts. Another aim was to explore if citizens could engage and understand research topics well enough to meaningfully contribute to the process of refining, enriching or just validating the research questions, and thus whether this approach was a viable strategy to potentially repeat in the future. The citizen working groups were asked to add, rephrase or confirm what experts had elaborated based on their own views, beliefs, interests and needs.

As this was an initial experiment, the project team could not guarantee that participant inputs would be included in the final official document, as the findings of the workshop were presented to the official authorities merely as a suggestion. Nevertheless, some of inputs were indeed integrated in the final agenda.

3.5.2 Recruitment, Types of Participants and Compensation

The UEFISCDI pilot was implemented in the context of two interactive workshops with citizens in the broadest sense. The recruitment process was commissioned to a recruitment company as UEFISCDI judged there weren't sufficient resources nor expertise to recruit a representative sample within the organization. UEFISCDI provided the following set of criteria for sampling participants: Gender balanced (50%-50%), geographical distribution (65%- big urban area, 15%- small urban area, 20%- rural area), level of education (70% - higher education, 30% - high-school/vocational school or lower), age (30% 20-30 years old, 30% 31-40 years old, 30% 41-50 years old, 10% 50+ years old). Participants received compensation in the form of a voucher provided by the recruitment company according to its internal compensation system.

The recruitment process went well, and the outcome met all the defined criteria. However, the team considers that better representation could have been possible if there had been more citizens above 50 years old. On the other hand, UEFISCDI had the impression that younger people have stronger opinions and a higher interest in getting involved in community issues, which would be beneficial to the process.

All participants received support materials at the beginning, and continuous advice/guidance by the facilitators throughout the whole activity.

3.5.3 Process and Participation Formats

The involvement of citizens in commenting and refining the national research agenda, took place in the context of two identical workshops on 13.05.2022 and 20.05.2022, held as physical events in Bucharest, Romania. Both workshops involved 30 citizens each, with 60 individuals participating in total. The participants were "regular" citizens, selected in such a manner as to provide some variety regarding their age, gender, level of education and geographic distribution between rural and urban areas. All recruited citizens took part in the workshop.

As a workshop format, a world café approach employing a foresight methodology was chosen, which makes use of an informal café setting for participants to explore an issue by discussing it in small groups at different thematic tables. This format was chosen due to its casual and accessible nature, which enabled all participants to share their opinions and to be listened to. Discussions were held in five rounds of 20-30 minutes within five working groups containing 6 citizens and one facilitator each. These discussions were divided into two stages, with each stage followed by a presentation of the discussion and a voting process on the inputs developed. In-between, participants changed working groups which exposed them to a variety of views and different information while they also had the opportunity to share their own perspectives with almost everyone taking part in the event. The world café technique builds on the notion of group intelligence and has the benefit that when bringing together the insights of small groups, the whole group has an opportunity to reach a broader perspective. Through this process, patterns could be identified and the drafted conclusion was relevant for all participants.

Thematically, UEFISCDI chose two topics from the Strategic Research Agenda to put up for discussion and debate among the participants: 1) Culture, creativity and inclusive society; and 2) Civil security for citizens. These two general topics included several impact areas framed as societal challenges that the research activity should try to tackle. Participants correlated the provided topics and research questions with their own personal endeavors and after several rounds of debates and voting sessions, they came

up with ten major issues that affect their lives and have a potential for being addressed through research and innovation activities. These issues were in turn thoroughly described and potential solutions and future developments were identified, including ideas about how the research process might contribute to solving the problem. A facilitator was the constant figure at the table supporting each working group. Their role included explaining the procedure, helping to engage everyone at the table, channeling the group dynamics, settling any potential issues, steering the process, and resolving any deadlocks.

In both iterations of the workshop, all participants were active, motivated, and shared their opinions and feedback in a friendly manner. They provided valuable contributions to the strategic documents and in their feedback made clear their enjoyment of the process. As hoped, the output generated by the expert panels was validated and enriched by the participating citizens. While both events were identical in terms of input, procedure, and format, the two groups identified different but still overlapping needs and challenges. For example, the quality of education was mentioned in both groups as a problem that affects everyone.

At the end of each event, all participants received an analogue feedback form to report on their drive to participate, their perception on their level of contribution, engagement and the interaction with the facilitators and the organisers, as well as a personal evaluation of the impact the event had on their opinions, beliefs, and know-how.

3.5.4 Frictions, Solutions and Lessons Learned

The pilot activity at UEFSCDI was mostly a novelty since the types of stakeholders usually engaged in the processes of the RFO are experts, researchers, policy-makers and business actors. The project team anticipated multiple challenges in relation to the involvement of citizens that might manifest throughout the process. Similarly to CDTI described below, the UEFSCDI pilot benefitted from analyzing the financial and human resources at the organization's disposal in order to make pragmatic decisions regarding the scope of the pilot and the distribution of tasks within the implementing team. **While the engagement format chosen by UEFSCDI was accessible, ensured equal contributions from all participants, and allowed for meaningful, horizontal interaction between them, it was ultimately quite resource intense.** As a consequence, only two workshops could be organized, involving a total of 60 citizens. These workshops, however, provided rich inputs to the National Strategic Research Agenda and left all actors in the process motivated. An important recommendation voiced by UEFSCDI is to **employ experienced facilitators** for such workshops, since it sometimes takes time and skill to engage all participants.

The pilot team at UEFSCDI was initially hesitant to involve citizens of lower educational backgrounds, fearing the process might be too far outside their comfort zone, making them unwilling or unable to constructively engage in the activity. This hesitancy was discussed in repeated conversations within the consortium and with the advisory board, ultimately leading UEFSCDI to the decision to open up the process and include a broader spectrum of the population. While the final group of participants was not entirely representative of the overall Romanian population, the UEFSCDI team lead still expressed her satisfaction with including a more diverse group of individuals, supported by the choice of engagement format: *"It was a unique experience to work with ordinary citizens and to watch how engaged they became throughout the development of the workshops and how professionally and productive their interaction with each other proved to be. [...] The most obvious lesson is that, provided that you have an appropriate context, a relevant topic for the target group, engaging citizens in serious matters is possible, even if they are out of their comfort zone."* (UEFSCDI Activity report) Finally, UEFSCDI also reflected on the usefulness of the Ethics Framework for the implementation of the pilot, which proved helpful in the definition of their activities as well as guiding the team in terms of fairness, transparency, equality and privacy. Reflecting on the document after completing the main pilot activities, the pilot team found that

“the Framework covers all the aspects that might seem sensitive or challenging when involving citizens in research related activities. The workshop has followed the Framework guidelines especially about involving a wide range of citizens, based on clear and fair criteria for recruiting participants - age and gender balanced, as well as a fair distribution between the rural and urban areas and according to their level of education. This approach was based on the Ethical Framework recommendations; hence, the document proves to be comprehensive, encompassing and inclusive enough.” (UEFISCDI Ethics Framework reflection)

3.5.5 Sustainability

As all actors involved in the UEFISCDI pilot perceived the pilot process as valuable and engaging, UEFISCDI is currently considering whether and how such citizen consultations might be established in the activities of the RFO in the future. Most workshop participants declared that they would like to participate at similar events in the future, in a similar context and environment, which provides further motivation for UEFISCDI to organize similar activities. However, no structured form of cooperation has been established and the main remaining question is how to replicate this kind of process at a larger scale, involving more citizens. UEFISCDI also contributes to an exploratory workshop as part of the Scientific Diaspora – Smart Diaspora 2023 conference that brings together RDI policymakers and representatives from RFOs, RPOs and industry. In the workshop *Promoscience – from citizen science to free access to European Research Infrastructures*, the PRO-Ethics project, Ethics Framework and Guidelines, as well as the UEFISCDI pilot and its outcomes will be highlighted.

3.6 Pilot 10: Evaluation of the Social Impact of the NEOTEC Program through a Participatory Approach (CDTI)

CDTI is a Spanish public organization for technology development and innovation answering to the Ministry of Science and Innovation. CDTI manages the Neotec funding program, which provides grants for New Technology-Based Firms (NTBs) to carry out projects that require the use of technologies or knowledge developed from research activities as well as a viable business plan. The objective of Neotec is to foster the transfer of knowledge from research organisations or expert teams to industry, seeing NTBs as a viable instrument to take scientific and technological progress generated in laboratories into the market, and in turn into society. Due to its multiple, direct and clear social implications, the Neotec program has been selected as a pilot to test new open evaluation approaches based on the participation of program beneficiaries. To this end, CDTI implemented 5 focus groups and a total of 30 interviews with various stakeholders, followed by an in-depth analysis of the gathered material.

3.6.1 Goals

The main goal of the participatory activity was to develop an evaluation methodology including evaluation criteria for measuring the social impact of RDI projects funded by Neotec for the first time. Further on, CDTI aims to apply the outcome of the participatory exercise in evaluating other internal funding programs, as well as disseminating it within its sphere of influence – mainly, regional innovation agencies and other public bodies in charge of RDI policy in Spain and the European evaluation community.

3.6.2 Recruitment, Types of Participants and Compensation

Considering the many types of activities set out in the two phases of the pilot, and the different types of stakeholders included in each of them, the requirements for recruiting participants varied. For example, for the first activity – a focus group with internal program managers at CDTI – warranted knowledge of the Neotec program and management experience, which was true also for the consultancy firms that had previously worked with Neotec, who were engaged in a second round of interviews. Additional

stakeholders were selected based on their relation to the entrepreneurship ecosystem, links between industry and academy, as representatives of vulnerable populations, and so on. An important cross-cutting criterion for the selection was the motivation and availability to participate in the evaluation process and a balanced representation in terms of technological area, gender and regional location. As per the internal uses and procedures of CDTI, none of the participants received compensation for their participation. Potential participants were randomly selected from the CDTI database according to the previously mentioned criteria. Firms' representatives were contacted via e-mail by the coordinator of the evaluation. Approximately 50% of the contacted firms agreed to participate in the evaluation. For the second phase, participants were selected by the members of the evaluation team, based on the previous stakeholder map defined in collaboration with the program managers.

3.6.3 Process and Participation Formats

While the PRO-Ethics team at CDTI has extensive expertise in quantitative impact evaluation methodologies, additional support, including expertise in qualitative methodologies, was needed to implement fieldwork such as data collection and treatment. To this end, CDTI engaged an external service provider with whom CDTI collaborated closely throughout the pilot. CDTI started out by mapping the potential stakeholder groups of the Neotec program, including all actors that theoretically could have been affected by the funding program, either intentionally or unintentionally, positively or negatively. As this exercise brought forth a very comprehensive network, it also became clear to CDTI that, pragmatically speaking, not all stakeholders within it could be engaged.

A first focus group was conducted with CDTI administrative management to review and validate the structure, processes and goals of the logic model for the pilot. In this context, expert inputs on qualitative evaluation methodology were also provided. The discussion focused on which questions should be answered through the evaluation, identification of relevant stakeholders to be involved in the evaluation, and relevant criteria for selecting beneficiaries of the program for the exploratory stage of the evaluation. The workshop was perceived as highly valuable and motivating, and led to three program managers joining the evaluation team.

This workshop was followed by interviews with various experts and stakeholders, including:

- ▶ “Social stakeholders”, i.e. umbrella organizations representing both sources of R&I initiatives and prospective users of innovations.
- ▶ External program managers from regional innovation agencies.
- ▶ Neotec program beneficiaries and consultancy firms giving support to tech start-ups

The semi-structured interviews aimed at further exploring what questions should be covered by the evaluation (i.e., what “information requirements” external stakeholders have regarding the impact of Neotec) and which societal stakeholders would be relevant to include in the evaluation process. The CDTI team received positive feedback from interview participants, who provided complementary perspectives on the Neotec program. Based on the inputs provided in these interviews, CDTI developed and pre-tested an online questionnaire, which was sent out to more than 1.300 companies who had been applying for Neotec funding between 2018 and 2022, of which 31% completed all questions. The questionnaire approached the impact of individual projects in relation to the SDGs (UN Sustainable Development Goals), with responses showing a strong positive correlation with health and quality of life, reducing the carbon footprint, and climate change mitigation in this self-assessment. While a positive relation with the digital divide was still quite pronounced, social inequality, quality education, poverty and social inclusion, and gender equality were much less in focus of Neotec-funded projects (see Figure 1). This information in turn may help policymakers decide on a potential change to the scope of the program, or whether to fund a different public initiative dedicated to addressing social issues.

Figure 1: Overview of self-reported data on the social problems addressed by companies participating in Neotec

Following the completion of all activities of this first stage of the pilot, all participants (except those answering the questionnaire) received a link to complete an online survey to assess their participatory experience, which directly fed into the internal evaluation of PRO-Ethics processes. The second stage of the pilot included the actual evaluation of the social impact of projects funded through the Neotec programme. Based on the collected information from all activities of the exploratory phase, CDTI managed to define new evaluation questions that open the scope of the project evaluation towards the assessment of social impact.

3.6.4 Frictions, Solutions and Lessons Learned

Overall, the process at CDTI went smoothly. While doubts were discussed quite openly by the pilot lead, potential issues were addressed proactively and most risks did not materialize into more severe issues. CDTI approached the entire process by clearly defining the evaluation process according to the logic model from the very beginning. **Thus, the pilot team had clarity regarding the scope and goals of the process, while it took great care to adjust its approach in an iterative process based on the learnings of each step.** CDTI also pointed out the importance of setting up the core implementing evaluation team. As external support was engaged for implementing the task, it was necessary to design the process within existing the official administrative procedures surrounding an open call for tenders. This needed **additional time** – several months, in fact – which had to be accounted for in the process. Furthermore, for this call terms of reference had to be drafted that **anticipated the necessary resources and flexibility** of implementing such a complex pilot. Open questions to be addressed were, for instance, how long the pilot would last in total, which data gathering instruments would be employed, and which unexpected events – unknown unknowns – might occur. As CDTI puts it, they had to “describe the profile of the experts in charge of the methodology and plan the resources requirements some months before starting the implementation of the Pilot.” (CDTI project manager, Pilot story #2) At the same time, this approach meant CDTI had accomplished designing the CDTI pilot in a very early stage of the PRO-Ethics project, which allowed them to apply the learnings from every activity carried out within the consortium from a very pragmatic approach.

On a more abstract level, the main point of friction can be defined as the **continuous adjustment of expectations and ambitions** necessary for a successful implementation of the pilot operating with limited time and budget. This approach of **managing resources proactively and anticipating bottlenecks** has been relevant in all stages of the process. For instance, the stakeholder map produced by CDTI was extremely comprehensive, including all possible stakeholders who potentially might be

impacted by the project activities funded through Neotec. As the CDTI's project manager rightfully pointed out, *"It is unfeasible to involve in the pilot all the stakeholders we have identified, and moreover, we could not be completely sure that all of them have something to say. And participation requires voices."*

In other words, when targeting a specific group or recruiting participants for participatory activities it is essential to keep in mind the limitations both at the organization, as well as at the participants' level. Similarly, **choosing the right participation format** to engage the intended stakeholder community and collect the data actually needed is key. CDTI mixed smaller, qualitative formats with a more quantitative survey to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the needs, interests and capacity of various stakeholder groups, while also developing a new approach to assessing the wider social impact of the Neotec program – and potentially other R&I funding instruments. While online meetings worked well with the engaged groups, CDTI found that holding in-person meetings in a friendly atmosphere was beneficial to having a fluid conversation. In any case, **support from professional facilitators** responsible for **time management**, and **focusing the conversation** was seen as helpful. In this context, CDTI also addressed questions of **bias among participants**. While focus group and interview participants were selected quite purposefully according to the expertise they brought to the table, in a workshop format it is important to allow for contrasting and complementary visions, which is another core task of the facilitator. CDTI also mentioned the need to **anticipate potential conflicts of interest**, which was especially pertinent in their pilot as CDTI was involving project beneficiaries in its processes. CDTI also found it crucial to select motivated participants with expertise and knowledge of the problems to be solved by the participatory activity. Here, clarity and transparency of the roles of actors in the process was again mentioned as an important factor of success. Informed consent procedures helped a lot to make clear the context of participation and the relevance of ethical aspects that are often ignored. On a similar note, providing participants with **guidelines on the issues to handle and the specific goals** may be helpful in creating transparency and in turn trustful collaborative relationships. Furthermore, CDTI took care to take participant inputs from these activities as guidelines for the actual evaluation, not as conclusions or findings already. As part of this, **ex-post reflection after each activity to share opinions and agree on core outputs was seen as essential** by the evaluation team. If this is not possible, drafting a reporting template that includes input also by the moderators, to be completed right after the activity, was identified as a good alternative. In any case, CDTI found **reporting to be as important as the activity itself**.

On a related note, ensuring **that all participants have a sufficient understanding of the process and what is needed from them is essential to receive meaningful responses**. For instance, while the response rate of the questionnaire sent out to companies was with 31% relatively good for an evaluation, CDTI had the impression that many potential respondents might have failed to see the connection between developing technology and contributing to the solution of social problems, i.e., creating a social impact. Thus, due to the framing of Neotec, such issues might be seen as beyond the scope of the program.

Finally, when collecting additional feedback from participants on their overall experience of the process or activity, their time and resources should also be taken into consideration. As PRO-Ethics employed an online survey for standardized participant feedback, CDTI advises such questionnaires should be as concise and closed as possible and collect this feedback right after the end of the activity itself. In the context of this pilot, feedback processes were further complicated by the fact that some of the involved experts had limited time availability.

3.6.5 Sustainability

In spite of the abovementioned points of friction, the overall result of the participatory activities of the pilot conducted at CDTI was very positive. After this pilot, the social impact will be incorporated as ex-

post evaluation criteria of Neotec and other CDTI programmes. Moreover, the evaluation questions defined in this exercise will be the background for further evaluations. This practice aims to give visibility to the effects that these policies could generate on the society in issues such as gender equality; access of population to technology; solutions of environmental and social problems; social inclusion and quality of the employment.

Based on the feedback collected in the course of the interviews and focus groups, CDTI found that participants were highly positive about their experience and the possibility of employing a participatory approach to evaluate a funding program. There was also a high degree of motivation from participants. Having understood that participation in the evaluation is completely free and has no effect on any administrative process related to the program, participants were very welcoming to the idea of conducting further participatory activities.

CDTI found that the Ethics Framework, and particularly the guidelines, had provided a useful reference to guarantee that participation was carried out according to ethical principles. Traditionally ethical issues were addressed only in terms of legal compliance, focusing especially concerning personal data protection. The application of the Framework provided a broader vision of this subject.

The new practices adopted on ethics have been very welcome by external stakeholders; they have received the message that their participation is handled in a formal way, following standardized procedures. From an internal point of view, these guidelines have provided the organization with useful tools to apply in forthcoming participatory processes. For example, the Informed consent form will remain as an internal working procedure for the CDTI Evaluation unit. Regarding the inclusion of ethics experts in the process, it would be better to include as a recommendation but not as a must, since many innovation agencies do not have access to ethics experts and this could discourage them to handle ethics issues. In fact, the guidelines should provide a framework reference to address ethical issues independently of experts.

CDTI plans to include participation of all the stakeholders involved in the evaluation in its comprehensive embedding event, bringing together social actors, program managers, beneficiaries, and policy makers.

3.7 Pilot 11: Engaging Citizens in Project/Proposal Evaluation – the Case of ETA (TA CR)

TA CR was an initial partner in the PRO-Ethics project. The RFO is a Czech government agency founded in 2009 with the aim of encouraging cooperation between research organizations supported by the state and the business sector. TA CR manages funds provided by the government, selected ministries (or ministry-like institutions) and international funds such as the Resilience and Recovery Fund (RRF). TA CR had planned to implement a pilot in the context of the SSH funding program ETA. However, by autumn 2021 it became clear that TA CR would not have sufficient funds for the planned calls in the ETA program, leaving the organization without a suitable program for carrying out the pilot. As a consequence, TA CR had to terminate its further participation in the PRO-Ethics project.

Reflecting on the main challenges that lead to this unfortunate situation, TA CR identified as a main barrier to the implementation of its pilot **decisions taken at the political level of R&D**, especially with regards to **flow of financial resources and call approval**. This was further exacerbated by **time restraints**, as political agreement by key stakeholders could not feasibly be achieved within the framework given by the PRO-Ethics project and the consensus at the time prioritized other sectoral priorities over social sciences and humanities. Furthermore, the **existing legal and institutional framework** presented a problem when an alternative pilot was sought, as without changes it was impossible to implement alternative participatory approaches as seen in other PRO-Ethics pilots. This, too, was exacerbated by

time pressures, as the adaptation of legal frameworks required to implement the desired changes were impossible to achieve on short notice.

While not considering this a main hurdle for the pilot but more of an observation interesting for the project, there were **reservations about the potential implementation of participatory activities in the context of TA CR among some of its employees**. The participation of experts was seen as quite welcome, while the participation of citizens was partly seen as something which would hinder processes at TA CR. This would not present a problem for the implementation of the intended TA CR pilot, as it was focused on the involvement of an academic group that were considered experts within the framework of the organization.

Finally, it is important to note that in the case of TA CR, the organizational leeway allowed by the organization's owner is quite low. TA CR puts up programs for approval and can officially design them how it sees fit, and negotiations between TA CR representatives and policymakers can try to steer things in the organization's favor depending on the state of the (R&D) political landscape. Nevertheless, with the influence of the sectoral priorities and political negotiations, choices on topic prioritization have to be taken depending on the approved state budget allocated for R&D.

4 Pilot Reflection Workshop (Brussels)

In the context of a general assembly meeting held in November 2022 in Brussels, the RFO partners of PRO-Ethics were guided by ZSI in a reflection workshop aimed at an exchange of experiences and to discuss the results and findings of their pilot activities. The workshop was divided into three sessions: 1) An **assessment exercise** used to visualize which challenges the RFO partners encountered within their pilot activities and if and how they could address them. 2) An image-based **picture card reflection** prompting RFO partners to share their most important findings. 3) An exchange on **learnings to transfer onto future activities**. These sessions will be described in more detail below.

4.1 Assessment Exercise

The first session of the workshop was an assessment exercise aimed at exemplifying which challenges the RFO partners encountered within their pilot activities and if and how they could address them. To this end, ZSI prepared a visual setting on the floor, consisting of 7 'stages' representing different ethical issues. These issues were based on the challenges identified in the course of the pilots and converted into statements serving as prompts for reflection by the RFO partners:

1. We defined the appropriate type of activity
2. We reached the number of participants planned
3. The group composition of our participants was balanced
4. Our process was transparent and clearly communicated
5. We could address conflicts of interests sufficiently
6. We managed to communicate in a comprehensive and understandable manner
7. We have tackled emerging ethical issues appropriately

To reflect on these questions, a representative of each RFO was positioned on a "starting line". From there, the participants were confronted with the statements laid out above. For each statement they could answer in the positive, they would take one step forward, giving a feeling of progression in terms of the ethical issues.

Figure 2: Assessment exercise of the reflection workshop

Stage 1: Appropriate Type of Activity: In the first stage, the RFO representatives were asked about the types of activity they applied in the context of their pilot. The partners mostly felt they had chosen the appropriate formats. For instance, FFG found the **variety of activities they employed adequate** to reach their aim of elaborating new call topics. Conversely, Innoviris reflected that **some of their activities were redundant and not worth the time and resources** they took to implement. Thus, while they were satisfied with their chosen methods to some extent, they also deemed them too ambitious, meaning in the future they would rather take a more focused approach. RCN reported that their digital Involve Hub meetings went fine. However, they had **difficulties convincing external experts to spend the time** to travel for the final, physical Hub meeting, so they decided to **adapt the format** and hold it online as well.

Stage 2: Planned Number of Participants: The second stage revolved around reaching the planned number of participants for activities, with three RFO representatives taking a step forward in response to the question. UEFISCDI employed a **recruitment company** in response to challenges encountered in previous activities. They **reached precisely the number of participants intended** and exhibiting the exact demographic characteristics sought from the group. VDI/VDE-IT built on a workshop with multipliers in the field and received 70 applications, from which they chose 15 participants. The RFO also felt the informative newsletter it issues was helpful, but also the **general motivation of the target group personally interested in the overall topic of the pilot**. FFG did not step forward as the RFO found it **difficult to estimate beforehand the concrete number of participants for each activity** it implemented. While the expert interviews were extended from three to 14, turnout for the validation workshop was lower than anticipated. For the online consultation, FFG thought it might reach up to 300 people, but reached only 123, which still included **much richer inputs than anticipated**. FFG went into the pilot conscious that adaptations would be necessary and reacted flexibly to adapt the aims of the pilot. The RFO concluded that it was **important to be flexible and respond to changing circumstances**.

Stage 3: Composition of Groups: Achieving a **balanced composition** of participants mostly worked out well for the pilot partners. Innoviris shared how they used a snowballing method with multipliers for their online survey, where representativity was not expected. For the citizen ateliers, on the other hand, they employed a sampling method that allowed for a good representation regarding socio-economic background, age, gender, and cultural background of residents of the Brussels Capital Region.

Stage 4: Transparency: The fourth stage assessed the clarity and transparency of communication with participants. VDI/VDE-IT was hesitant, as the team tried to communicate the processes and steps of the pilot clearly but found that, despite their best efforts, some **information was lost in translation or did not get through to participants**, so this would be an area that could still be improved. As R&I processes might be hard to understand for people unexperienced in them, and the pilot is overall new to the field, everyone was rather unsure of their roles. This was further exacerbated by the fact that the RFO wanted **participants to have flexibility, which sometimes left them lost within this freedom**.

Stage 5: Conflicts of Interest: At the fifth stage, the RFO partners were asked whether they had addressed conflicts of interest sufficiently. While most of the present RFOs did not encounter any such conflicts, Innoviris experienced a **political veto** which forced them to take down their social media recruitment campaign. The reason given was that the slogans Innoviris employed were too politically sensitive. As there was **not enough time for further negotiations**, the pilot partner opted instead to switch to a street recruitment campaign, which turned out to be challenging in its own right, as it was **time-intensive and yielded less engaged participants**. Thus, this intervention really impacted this pilot activity.

Stage 6: Comprehensibility: The sixth stage assessed whether the pilot partners were able to communicate in a comprehensibly manner. FFG mentioned how this issue was **difficult to judge**. The

RFO put a lot of effort **adjusting the complexity of their questionnaire**, and in turn received a lot of feedback. However, their respondents were **self-selected and highly biased** towards well-educated women between 40 and 60, who showed the most interest and provided rich qualitative inputs. This bias might have been exacerbated due to the **legally required privacy statement** put at the beginning.

Stage 7: Tackling Ethical Issues: The last stage inquired whether the pilot partners felt they had tackled ethical issues appropriately as they came up. The partners felt they were **aware of ethical issues and generally successful in addressing them**, with no major challenges reported. RCN, for example, invited stakeholders already interested in ethical issues in their own right, so this topic was front and center. Reflections were had in terms of group composition to invite diverse participants, although not all participants attended the Hub meetings.

Additional Question: Did you use the *Ethics Framework* for the planning of their activities? In general, *Ethics Framework* supported the pilot partners in considering ethical issues. UEFISCI, for instance, tried to apply it in terms of communication, transparency, fairness, interaction with participants, and so on. While they can be regarded as common-sense principles, it would be important to have **practical examples to make the framework more tangible**. Thus, similarly to what was seen in the TAFTIE workshop, there is an expressed need for very specific requirements to be contained in the *Framework*.

4.2 Picture-Card Reflection

In the second session, RFO representatives were prompted to choose two images from a collection of picture cards that would reflect their most important findings. Their experiences can be summarized thusly:

- ▶ **CDTI:** Participatory processes are often nebulous and complicated. There is no one-size-fits-all process; rather, it needs to be adapted to the concrete context.
- ▶ **VDI/VDE-IT:** There is always a tension between how much freedom should be allowed versus how much directions participants are given. In terms of group dynamics, everyone should be equal and part of a good team, which is difficult when some people are very loud and have strong opinions, while others go under the radar, so facilitation is needed. Sometimes we also work with vulnerable groups, so it reminded me of putting the human in the center of the things we are doing. It takes really a lot of effort and planning and knowing very precisely also what our aims are when we want to do participation.
- ▶ **Innoviris:** For participatory processes, there is no one fits all solution. Everyone is dealing with the same challenges, but there is not one answer to all the questions. So we have to surf on the wave of experimenting with participatory practices. But it is very helpful to have the guidance of experts in addressing practical and operational questions. Participatory practices in RFOs are still in their infancy, so everybody is still discovering.
- ▶ **FFG:** It is very pleasant working with stakeholders and citizens and developing new things. It is also necessary to have the time and resources to bring out what is in there. This is often lacking at funding agencies, where it's difficult to find the calm to really work on things and not rush through everything like most of us are used to. We want to focus all participants on the same question, but some are distracted and drop out, and we don't know why. Also, they are not a very mixed group, which was one of our challenges. We are navigating a field by taking many small decisions and the sum of the decisions determine where we end, and you don't know that in the beginning.

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- ▶ **RCN:** At least in the beginning, it felt like it was quite a long way to go to ensure we can implement what we planned. We had to talk to decision makers and so on, but we managed at least to do the most important things that we planned to. If you have different kinds of perspectives and backgrounds, and they supplement each other, they can come together like ingredients in a great dish.
 - ▶ **UEFISCDI:** We had diverse opinions, like a lot of colors, diverse citizens with their own needs and interests, and we had to put them together somehow and they are all going the same way, so eventually they come up with a narrative that suited them all.

4.3 Learnings for Future Activities

In the last session, the RFO partners were asked to reflect on their insights so far and how to carry them on in future activities. In groups of two RFOs each, they exchanged on their first steps in embedding the learnings of the pilot activities and what to consider in implementing further participatory approaches in their home institutions. The flipcharts created by the three groups can be found in Annex 2.

In group 1 (Innoviris and RCN), Innoviris pointed out that they would like to continue these kinds of participatory approaches, but as such processes are costly in terms of time and money, the question is how to continue, especially in days of austerity. Can the work be continued in a more cost-effective manner? Perhaps synergies to other initiatives could be exploited. Maybe, instead of a series of small activities, one bigger participatory activity can be undertaken but less often. In terms of institutional embedding, although Innoviris had been experimenting with participatory activities for quite some while, there is still a lot of skepticism; and the pilot team is not sure whether this is a feasible approach to them as a research funding agency.

The situation at RCN is different, as the Hub gatherings are not very costly. Furthermore, the RFO has already an established working group on how to better integrate different areas of open research into the organization's processes. Nevertheless, questions of time and resources still weigh heavily, even more so as the Research Council just underwent significant budget cuts. While the *Ethics Framework* will be considered within the funding schemes and might be translated into Norwegian, it is not yet clear how it will be integrated, as calls at RCN are mostly based on the ministries. Then again, the ministries are also very concerned with citizen participation.

In group 2 (FFG and VDI/VDE-IT), FFG equally found that implementing participatory processes requires intense forethought and planning, as well as a lot of time and resources. As such, activities cannot be squeezed into the organization's regular work. Therefore, the pilot team needs to demonstrate an impact of the activity in order to justify the additional efforts. FFG also found that the ministries providing the call budget were supportive and really interested in joining the pilot workshops. But this still does not mean that FFG will receive more funds to cover its administrative costs, and additional support to implement such processes on a broader basis.

This is also true for VDI/VDE-IT, which added that there was a need for the funding ministry to have trust in the agency, and for that it needs to be sure that the pilot team is doing a good job. The RFO pointed out that, to some extent, persuasion was required, as participatory processes and letting people decide on funding or call topics also entails giving up some power, both for the ministries and the funding agencies.

Finally, in group 3 (UEFISCDI and CDTI), UEFISCI shared they had finished the core of their participatory activity and already had some results at hand, which allowed them to try to implement similar events and engagement activities in the future. However, the right contexts conditions must be identified. The

pilot was based on a very concrete official document that could be tested with citizens. This was helpful, but not all such documents are fit for such an approach, so this is an open question still to be figured out. On a similar note, while the format worked really well for the pilot, it would be interesting to experiment with it a bit more, like for example changing the group size. In any case, UEFISCDI was sure that physical meetings worked better than online ones, especially for the lay participants they engaged, and would not change this in future iterations.

CDTI laid out that they were still very much in the process of implementing their pilot activity, but at the time encountered some technical problems and thus had to limit the scope of their evaluation. The RFO found that timing is critical; and December was not a good month for participatory activities due to end-of-the-year workloads and the holiday season. CDTI at that point in time had finished its exploratory phase, which was like a complete pilot in its own right, and moved towards implementing an online survey and focus groups with business representatives and program managers.

5 Evaluation Workshop (Copenhagen)

At the third and final cross-pilot learning workshop held in March 2023 in Copenhagen, ZSI organized an evaluation workshop with the project's RFO partners, which was implemented in collaboration with DBT. **The following workshop summary is an excerpt from a more detailed chapter in D3.3 Report on Cross-Pilot Workshop Activities (primary author Elsa Alves).**

From the PRO-Ethics consortium, five out of six RFO partners were present, namely Innoviris, FFG, VDI/VDE-IT, RCN and UEFISCDI. Open Call grantee LBG also joined the workshop and shared its experiences. CDTI could not join the workshop, but provided additional inputs in written form on all the questions discussed at the meeting.

The session started with a mapping exercise laying out the basic facts of each pilot, identifying their target groups, wider stakeholder communities, recruitment and engagement formats, goals and intended impacts (see chapter 3 for more information). From there, the RFO partners were asked to identify the biggest barriers and drivers of achieving the intended goals and impacts of their pilots.

5.1 Impact Barriers

A number of barriers towards achieving impact through the implementation of participatory processes were identified by the pilot partners:

1. Designing a method where citizens provide sufficient input to be taken into consideration by experts/researchers
2. Communicating to citizens the benefits of their interaction in the participatory process when reaching out for the purposes of recruitment and engagement activities
3. Involving a broader spectrum of stakeholders/participants
4. A lack in terms of (internal and external) institutionalization of participatory engagement in RDI with expertise and experience in ethical engagement
5. Understanding the culture of the RFO and breaking down certain elitist and hierarchical discourses
6. Differences leading to biases within the citizen council (e.g. different levels of knowledge, motivation, engagement in other networks, etc. creating tension in the group)
7. Balancing the ethical approach throughout the process: it is an ongoing process with different steps, therefore new ethical problems arise
8. Veto from ministry stemming from friction between policy and politics
9. Finding the right timing (taking into consideration the season, holidays, exams and the time of day)
10. Reaching out to vulnerable citizens (e.g. unhoused people)
11. Calibrating the selection of participants, as an adjustment of the target group entails also an adjustment in the process and methodology

During this exchange in the plenary, the ethical challenges of the pilots were more in focus than the process-related ones. For instance, trying to ensure that everyone participates on equal terms raises significant questions. Citizens have different needs and expectations and some of them wish to be more involved, which brings into question whether the RFO should impose a limit to their willingness and freedom of participation. This aspect was echoed by another RFO that stressed the need for constant ethical checks throughout the process. Carrying out a participatory approach means constant interaction, bringing forth constant ethical issues that need to be tackled and negotiated.

5.2 Impact Drivers

Regarding the drivers for reaching intended impacts, the RFO partners stated their most helpful decisions as follows:

-
1. Creating a narrative (ethically sound and practically feasible) describing the process, methodology, impact/goals
 2. Securing sufficient funding for implementing the activity
 3. Creating a cross-cutting project team that represents the organization at different levels in a holistic approach of ethical participatory engagement and works on an internal, national and international level, adapting the learnings from the pilot to the institutional profile
 4. Management support
 5. Involving all relevant stakeholders already in the conceptualization of the process
 6. Working with local citizen participation experts and taking in their advice in the preparation and implementation of the pilot
 7. Participation being already at the heart of the current policy priorities

The identified drivers and barriers reveal to a degree the specific nature of RFOs, insofar as they are dependent on external funding, the political momentum, and the culture of their organization i.e., the degree of internal institutional anchoring and openness to carry out the participatory activities with the desirable impact. It is particularly apparent through the pilots' experiences that effective organizational change and uptake of a participatory approach is subject to institutional support. Furthermore, it was generally seen as a good principle to adopt a co-creation approach from the start, involving stakeholders already in the research and design phases of the process. In addition, the RFO who experienced a veto from the ministry stressed the importance of seeking contractual agreements with all parties, especially political ones, detailing the plans from the beginning in order to avoid similar roadblocks.

5.3 Most Important Lessons Learned

The last part of the discussion was focused on discussing the outcomes and lessons learned, participants were asked what the most significant change achieved through the pilot was (and/or will be), what the most important learning from the pilot was, and what made the process worth it so far.

Regarding the most significant change achieved through the pilot, the RFO partners reported the following:

1. One RFO's institutional position in the research system will be elevated, as it was able to position itself as a crucial actor for ethics of involvement as an integrated dimension of a holistic RFO policy/practice for more open RDI.
2. One RFO experienced a change in calls for proposal by opening up their invitations in direction of open research.
3. One RFO experienced its results as helpful to determine when and where citizen participation has a value, and how much to invest in such a process.

Positive changes are also expected to happen in the future, such as the development of a dedicated funding program taking into account participatory engagement methodologies. Overall, the piloting experience was quite positive in a variety of dimensions. Some RFOs stressed the importance of the pilots being anchored within institutions that made them learn-by-doing and now they understand some of the possibilities and challenges related to participatory engagement. An iterative and agile approach to participation was deemed preferential over trying to implement a ready-made but rigid model. Although participatory engagement approaches are gaining traction in several spheres of society, the RFO representatives agreed that there is no one-size-fits-all solution, and the pilot learnings may become a source of orientation and inspiration in the field. Furthermore, and from a broader perspective, the process of piloting helps bring citizens closer to academia, narrowing the gap between the research superstructure and society. This, in turn, might increase trust of citizens in science and innovation. In addition, by listening more to the needs and concerns of citizens, a greater societal impact may be achieved. Complex societal challenges may thus be tackled in more adequate ways and social mission goals reached more effectively.

6 Workshops with TAFTIE

To foster collaboration between the PRO-Ethics consortium and the TAFTIE network, a series of two collaborative workshops was designed and implemented by ZSI. These events were meant to introduce and discuss the *Ethics Frameworks*, but also to more generally strengthen ethical participatory processes undertaken by research funding organizations across Europe. The first workshop took place online on 12. May 2022. Set for 1,5 hrs., it was aimed at giving participants an introduction to the PRO-Ethics project and allowing for limited space for discussion. With four of the PRO-Ethics RFO partners and eleven TAFTIE member representatives participating, a total of 17 stakeholders actively engaged in the interactive event, covering a wide range of countries across Europe.

Figure 3: Map of the geographic distribution of workshop participants

Agenda	
Welcome & warm up	9.30
Introduction to PRO-Ethics	9:45
Presentation of PRO-Ethics pilots & discussion	10:00
Wrap up and outlook	10:55

Table 1: Agenda of the first TAFTIE workshop

After a short welcome and introduction to the workshop and the PRO-Ethics project, the participants received insights into the different pilot activities, with the consortium’s RFO partners giving detailed presentations of their experiences within their participatory pilot activities. Participants were also able to ask questions, make suggestions, as well as explore potentials and possibilities and discuss national differences. The following pilot topics were presented:

- i. Evaluation of the social impact of the NEOTEC programme from a participative approach (CDTI Spain)
- ii. New modes of engaging citizens in topic identification and programme design (VDI/VDE-IT Germany)
- iii. Citizen participation learning hub (RCN Norway)
- iv. Citizen participation in topic definition (FFG Austria)

In the following discussion, a few questions were raised from the audience to be taken into account in the further development of the *Ethics Framework*:

- ▶ How to distinguish between citizens and scientists, and how to negotiate double roles people find themselves in?
- ▶ How to motivate and incentivize participants? How to handle reimbursements?
- ▶ How to approach the selection of participants? How important is representativeness?
- ▶ How do you involve non-technical people in the assessment of technical projects, and how do you best communicate technical issues?
- ▶ How can the knowledge developed in PRO-Ethics be transferred to other agencies?

The second, longer and more interactive workshop took place on 3. November 2022 and was also held online. Unfortunately, between a rival event, sick leave and family emergencies, a lot of prospective and already registered participants had to excuse themselves. In the end, four PRO-Ethics RFO partners and nine external stakeholders took part in the workshop, for a total of 13 participants, enabling a lively discussion.

Agenda	
Welcome & warm up	9.30
Presentation of the <i>Ethics Framework</i>	9:55
Presentation of ethical challenges encountered in 4 PRO-Ethics pilots	10:15
Discussion and collection of needs for a practical guideline, identification of blind spots	10:45
Presentation of results	11:30
Closing and feedback	11:45

Table 2: Agenda of the second TAFTIE workshop

At the beginning of the workshop, consortium partner TUD gave a presentation on the preliminary version of the *Ethics Framework* as it was current at the time:

Figure 4: Presentation by TUD on the Ethics Framework

To prepare for the workshop, the participating pilot partners UEFISCDI, FFG, CDTI and VDI/VDE-IT were asked to provide reflections on the ethical challenges they had encountered so far in the implementation of their pilots. ZSI developed an overview presentation of these challenges (see Annex 3), which was shared by ZSI, with input from the RFO partners, after the TUD presentation. Moving on to the interactive part of the workshop, the named challenges were broadly clustered into four thematic fields:

Figure 5: Collection of thematic fields

Based on this input, the participants were invited to discuss their perspectives in two small breakout groups. The discussion was captured on a Miro board and presented in a final plenary. Screenshots of the Miro boards can be found in Annex 3.

Group 1 discussed how it was important to make clear who the target groups of the *Ethics Framework* would be, and how much experience they would have in public engagement. While the document should be a supporting tool to make sure ethical questions are addressed, guidelines are still less helpful than experiences. In any case, the document could be helpful in the standardization of such processes and in creating a shared language to communicate. This would be especially helpful as some currently available guidance asserts there was no need for an ethics review of participatory processes, which is for instance the current legal situation in the UK. Furthermore, experts currently evaluate projects according to excellence, but ethics is more than just excellence and research integrity: It includes the impacts of projects, how outputs will be implemented, by which actors and in which contexts.

Nevertheless, in the discussion it was pointed out that participation is not a goal but an instrument, and it was essential to both adapt our processes to participation, and to adapt participation to our processes. The *Ethics Framework* should be a tool to guide this process, explore blind spots, and support reflection. The group also pointed out the difference between the ethics of involvement and the ethics of engagement, stressing the need to empower people to be engaged in a participatory process. This question is partly related to the issue of compensation, which might mean different things in different contexts. In any case, it is important to find ways to integrate monetary compensation into the scheme of a project.

Finally, in discussing the concrete value of the *Ethics Framework*, group 1 found it important that the document help researchers and other academic actors understand that ethics is not just a bureaucratic box-ticking exercise, but makes processes better. Thus, it would be helpful to add concrete examples from researchers in the field. The *Framework* should further contribute to capacity building in R&I ecosystems, developing and pushing up the overall level of expertise on ethical engagement practices. As one workshop participant pointed out: We haven't had a problem yet, but maybe that's because we are not looking. This also points towards the problem that people currently don't have the resources to do ethics well. Thus, institutional change is needed to allow for the time, money, expertise, and resources needed to improve such processes. In any case, the participants of group 1 found that taking care to involve the public as early in a process as possible gives it the highest chances of success.

Group 2 found that the *Ethics Framework* confirmed many of the requirements and needs that must be considered when conducting participatory processes. The group collected a number of topics, solutions, and gaps and recommendations for the *Framework*. These included:

Which stakeholders should be involved, and which shouldn't? Some people might better be excluded because they might disturb the process. This also touches on questions of potential conflicts of interest. Here, it is important to be transparent with all involved actors about the process, its different steps and activities, and the roles everyone plays in it. In terms of recommendations, the group termed this thematic area *stakeholder management*, which has to be considered throughout the process for it to be successful.

What knowledge is needed, and which groups should be represented? While some knowledge might already be represented in the implementing team, it is always helpful to contact gatekeepers and multipliers in the field to gain access and knowledge. To avoid overlooking and missing groups, it is important to look for diversity and heterogeneity in the group, to leave the comfort zone and not settle on the easy ways of doing things. The *Ethics Framework* should provide support in how to deal with

heterogeneous groups, how to be sensitive about differences in the group and how to facilitate a constructive and meaningful process.

Involvement of marginalized groups: It is important to be aware that there might be different kinds of trauma within these groups, so it is essential to be sensitive to different experiences, situations, life histories, psychological statuses, and so on, and to be mindful of and safeguard the boundaries of actors in the process. As a researcher, it is important to be authentic, honest, and reflective of one's own role, while avoiding giving top-down advice. Not only is respectful interaction key, but expert consultations, including with psychologists and community and advocacy groups, might be needed. Regarding the *Framework*, theoretical input on how to work with marginalized groups, like a short list on instructions, would be helpful.

Language and translation: It is important to reflect on the vocabulary used in a process to make it accessible to the target group. Even more, it is important to not expect participants to express themselves perfectly and phrase their contributions according to scientific paradigms. Rather, translation and re-translation between different spheres of communication is needed, guiding participants through the process step by step, employing different formats such as pictures, scenarios, and so on. The process also benefits from allowing participants to contribute at multiple points.

Values: We must always be aware of what we communicate in the participatory process, what values and attitudes are transported, to create a positive experience for all actors and avoid participation fatigue. This also helps in recruitment and keeping people engaged over prolonged periods of time.

7 Summary and Discussion

The implementation of the PRO-Ethics pilots of phase II was tied to a larger ambition of developing and testing a standardized tool to support the implementation of ethical participatory processes (the *Ethics Framework and Guidelines*), identifying best practices, finding levers to adapt institutional processes and embed our learnings in regional and national R&I ecosystems across Europe. These multifaceted playing fields are reflected in the pilot processes and the concrete lessons that could be extracted from them.

For one thing, various internal and external dependencies influencing the success of participatory processes in the context of research funding organizations could be identified. On a purely structural level, funding agencies are dependent on political decision makers, usually ministries, that provide budgets for funding programs and often co-define R&I agendas. As the case of TA CR shows, this might mean entire funding programs have to be paused, and with it any potential for participatory real-life experiments. At the same time, even highly interested and engaged ministries, as were present in the pilots of FFG, RCN, VDI/VDE-IT and to a degree Innoviris, might not automatically provide support such as the additional funding needed to implement a participatory process at the necessary level of quality. Not only are additional resources needed – including for administrative costs – but participation is about involving wider stakeholder groups in decision making processes, and thus entails ministries and funding agencies having to give up some of their power. Otherwise, meaningful participation would not be possible. Thus, anchoring participatory processes within research funding organizations needs actionable support beyond lip service.

Meaningful buy-in is consequently needed on both the level of policy and an organizational level. Internal skepticism about the validity of participatory methodologies and the benefit of expending additional efforts has to be overcome, which makes it all the more important to demonstrate the impact such approaches may have. This is deeply tied to the need to develop a clear understanding of the scope, ambition, but also the available resources from very early on in a participatory process. This has been perceived as very helpful in the cases of CDTI and UEFISCDI, who identified gaps in their internally available expertise and decided early on in the pilot to involve external experts. This not just removed pressure from the pilot partners but forced them to define certain timeframes and criteria of their participatory activities at the very beginning, when the contracts with external service providers were negotiated. This can be contrasted with the experience of Innoviris, who also involved an external expert organization but much later in the pilot, on very short notice, and only in response to political interference blocking their initial plan. The efforts expended in this context – both in terms of budget and sheer labor of street recruitment – did not yield the desired results, which in turn negatively impacts the potential for future participatory engagement attempts at the RFO.

All this points towards the complexity inherent to participatory processes, which need a lot more additional time and resources, flexibility and capacity to adapt, forethought and planning, as well as knowledge and expertise than the established and institutionalized processes that make up the daily routines of research funding organizations. With participatory engagement, there is no one-size-fits-all solution; rather, each process must be adapted to the specific goals, problem definitions, target groups, and framework conditions at hand. To complicate things further, these have to be somewhat anticipated beforehand, while still remaining open to respond to changing circumstances. Limited resources and tight timelines can have a significantly negative impact on a project even if it has institutional backing and previous expertise. Returning once more to the case of Innoviris, certain formats took longer to implement due to technological issues, which led to less time to recruit participants for follow-up activities. When the chosen recruitment format was vetoed, this left even less time to adapt. The

situation was even further exacerbated by the time of year the activities took place, which was the end of the school year and the beginning of the summer holidays, contributing to an overall low turnout. Interestingly, CDTI encountered the very same challenge for their activities set in December. Thus, choice of timing is critical beyond RFO-internal factors such as call release dates.

Such issues as described above can be mitigated by involving key stakeholders such as politicians and other decision-makers from early on in the process. In response to the veto, Innoviris even suggests seeking contractual agreements with all parties, especially political ones, detailing the plans from the beginning in order to avoid similar roadblocks. This touches on the need for clear communication and transparency with all actors involved in a participatory process, regarding the goals and individual steps of a process, but also its scope and limitations as well as the intended roles of all collaborators. Through this, trust may be built and expectations managed, reducing the risk for misunderstandings, disappointments and other types of friction. Here, informed consent procedures already established in the context of R&I projects were found to be helpful, as they clarify at least some core aspects of the process for all involved parties.

Still, as apparent in the descriptions of this deliverable, clear communication and transparency might be easier said than done. As VDI/VDE-IT pointed out, some information might just get lost in translation, some processes and topics might be hard to understand for people unexperienced to them, and as processes unfold in real time, even the implementing parties might experience uncertainties about their roles. Also, putting too much on participants in too little time might become a burden in its own right. In this context, certain trade-offs become readily apparent: Giving participants a great amount of freedom might leave them lost, while giving them too strict a process to operate in might hinder meaningful participation. Being too ambitious might leave involved parties on all sides frustrated and disappointed, while too little ambition might leave a process shallow. Even more, it might be questioned whether a process can truly be seen as participatory if it lacks a certain depth⁶. In any case, on a limited budget, decisions must be made about the breadth and depth of engagement. As UEFISCDI pointed out, the chosen format was accessible, ensured equal contributions from all participants, and allowed for meaningful, horizontal interaction between them, it was ultimately quite resource intense, which is why it had to be limited to two workshops with 30 participants each. Furthermore, such qualitative formats can only unfold their value if they are carefully planned and implemented, with multiple pilot partners stressing the importance of experienced facilitators in the implementation of interactive formats.

In any case, it is essential to choose the right participation format to engage the intended stakeholder community and collect the data actually needed. To this end, it was seen as helpful for some pilots to engage experts and multiplier organizations with knowledge of and access to the field, and to address both practical and operational questions. This is also important for the identification of existing barriers to participation relevant to the target group. In the context of our pilots, these included socio-economic pressures, educational levels, digital literacy, (child-)care duties, language barriers, and general time restraints, to name just a few. Organizations implementing participatory processes must on the one hand ensure they develop an understanding of these barriers and the needs of the engaged communities and individuals. On the other hand, these factors might also impact the dynamics of a group and need to be handled carefully when implementing interactive formats. Time is a factor here as well: VDI/VDE-IT, who set up a stable group collaborating over several years, had to address much more

⁶ For instance, taking as a frame of reference Arnstein's ladder of participation, to move beyond tokenisms it is essential to give citizens some degree of power in a process. See Sherry R. Arnstein (1969) A Ladder Of Citizen Participation, Journal of the American Institute of Planners, 35:4, 216-224, DOI: 10.1080/01944366908977225 but also the IAP2 Spectrum of Public Participation, where a current version may be found on the IAP2 website <https://www.iap2.org/mpage/Home>

complex interpersonal dynamics than UEFISCDI, who employed a similarly interactive but much more limited engagement format. For VDI/VDE-IT, the desired diversity of the group laid open gaps between participants regarding their knowledge of certain topics, overall time and resources, as well as their motivation and capacity to contribute, which became more pronounced over time. Here, a balance needs to be found where the efforts of more engaged members can be valued and utilized, while less engaged members or those with fewer resources are not overwhelmed by the complexity of the process or the workload and are still enabled to make meaningful contributions. This tension can also be mitigated, at least in part, by allowing for some variety in the formats or intensities of participation. In the case of VDI/VDE-IT's citizen advisory board, some members who felt more secure in their presentation could for instance act as spokespersons for the CAB in the proposal evaluation procedure with the scientific evaluation board.

VDI/VDE-IT, FFG, CDTI and RCN all found that personal interest or having a direct stake in a topic helped in receiving richer inputs. Still, this is very much dependent on the format of interaction. RCN and VDI/VDE-IT, for instance, were both unable to establish digital exchange processes for their participants outside of dedicated pilot activities (i.e., workshops and meetings) that were somewhat independent of RFO facilitation and direction. Both the Signal group for informal caregivers and the exchange platform for Hub participants couldn't gain momentum and were abandoned relatively swiftly.

In any case, ex-post reflection after each activity – within the implementation team but depending on the process also with participants – was seen as essential to remain agile, adapt the process in a timely manner, and maintain its overall quality.

7.1 Sustainability

To outline the sustainability of the efforts undertaken in the PRO-Ethics project, a distinction must be made between several levels:

At the organization level, the main question pertains to the future of participatory engagement within the RFOs of PRO-Ethics. In this respect, FFG and UEFISCDI are considering a continuation of their pilot activities, while VDI/VDE-IT already established for the pilot to continue beyond the project. All three RFOs are in negotiations with funding ministries to explore the options towards institutionally anchoring such processes within each agency. RCN might continue Hub activities beyond PRO-Ethics, but was in any case able to leverage the pilot activities to create lasting networks on citizen engagement in processes of scientific knowledge production. Innoviris felt the greatest gap between the efforts extended in the context of the pilot, and the outcomes it yielded. The RFO is currently in conversation with other important regional stakeholders on the strategic development of a center of expertise on citizen engagement that would make such processes less risky and more plannable in the future. Finally, CDTI achieved a very specific goal with its pilot, namely the development of an evaluation methodology to identify relevant questions on social impact related to Neotec and evaluate the overall social impact of the program. After this pilot, social impact will be incorporated as evaluation criteria at the CDTI. Moreover, the evaluation questions defined in this exercise will be the background for further evaluations. With these goals being achieved, CDTI has currently little incentive to follow up the pilot, but is open to this should a suitable problem area present itself.

Regarding the *Ethics Framework*, the pilots were essential in testing and further developing the document for future use. While the applicability of the *Framework* for internal RFO processes depends on whether the organization intends to implement participatory activities in the future, it is also an option to make the document available to projects employing participatory methodologies or using it as a basis for conversations around ethics between different stakeholders, including researchers and ethics committees. RCN and FFG have been the most positive RFO partners regarding the future use of the

Ethics Framework in their organizations and beyond. Innoviris, similarly, could see the *Framework* as being useful for the activities of the center of expertise on citizen engagement and integrating the basic principles of the *Framework* in their functioning. The RFO is also considering developing potential scenarios for the future based on the framework. UEFISCDI could use the document in case activities similar to their PRO-Ethics pilot can indeed be implemented, as is currently anticipated. VDI/VDE-IT would employ the *Framework* in case participatory formats have a future at the agency, and is currently working dissemination activities to give the document broader visibility in Germany, including a paper manuscript on the evaluation of participatory processes and a potential training on the *Framework* in an upcoming embedding event. CDTI focused its processes on ethical aspects in participatory evaluation and will keep building on such formats in the future evaluation processes. As such, the *Framework* will be included in the agency's operative processes.

Annex 1: Activity Report Template

Dear RFO partner!

This template must be filled in to report on all your engagement activities. The report will be the basis for gathering and synthesizing your experiences and it will serve as basis for the cross learning activities in WP3. It aims at monitoring all pilot II cases, supports you in reflecting and evaluating your activities and will feed into D2.4 “Reports on pilot II results” where all experiences and reflections will be summarized and publicly be made accessible.

The document is structured in two sections:

1. Data collection on participants and engagement activity
2. Activity report – narrative section

Make sure to report **each of your engagement activity**, for instance in a series of workshops – report after each workshop.

Please send the filled in template **in near-time after each activity** to our ZSI mailing list: proethics@zsi.at

Thank you!

Section 1: Data collection for monitoring

- ▶ Engagement activity number⁷:
- ▶ Date:
- ▶ Location:
- ▶ Total number of citizens/users/researchers/firms/experts included:
- ▶ Type of activity (e.g. focus group):
- ▶ Repeat of a previous activity: Y/N,
 - if Y, please indicate which (number)
- ▶ Compensation for the participants (if any):
- ▶ Support for the participants (e.g. training, advice, materials, ...):
- ▶ Planned follow-up activities:

Please fill in per participant (if number of participants allows this detailed information):

Participant No.	Gender (f/m/d)	Age	Country	Specific skills	Group (citizens, users, researchers, firms, experts)	Profession
1						
2						
3						

⁷ Please start with 1 and count all activities one after the next

4						
5						
Etc.						

Section 2: Activity report

This is a narrative section. Please take your time, as this document will be the basis for gathering and synthesizing your experiences and it will serve as basis for the cross learning activities in WP3. Thus, please be as detailed and honest as possible. Describe your experiences, reflect the processes and think about possible improvements.

- ▶ Title of engagement activity:
- ▶ Goals and non-goals of your engagement activity (SMART⁸):

Please describe and reflect the following:

- ▶ Explain your mapping and recruitment process

What worked well, what did not work? What would you improve? What do you recommend to others?

- ▶ Methodological structure of engagement activity (Explain here how the engagement activity was set up. Which engagement formats/methods did you choose and why?)

How did it work? What would you improve and what would you recommend to others?

- ▶ If you employed qualitative feedback activities such as focus groups or similar, please describe your results. (If you did not apply a feedback session, leave this field open)

⁸ SMART concept: S – specific, M – measurable, A – attainable, R – realistic, T - timely

► General reflections: Reflect about this engagement activity.

What hurdles and challenges did you encounter in implementing the participatory process?	
Have (sustainable) cooperations with citizens or civil society organisations been established? Will these cooperations continue after the end of the process?	
Do the results of the process feed into other activities or projects?	
How did you experience the participatory process?	
What are the lessons learnt you take from the process?	
Which new questions have arisen from the process?	
Are there any follow-up projects or any further projects on similar issues planned?	
Do you have any concrete suggestions on how to improve the Ethics Framework?	
What was your experience using/implementing the Ethics Framework and Guidelines (in)to your pilot work? (Provide examples)	

Annex 2: Photos Brussels Workshop

Figure 6: Flipchart group 1 – Innoviris and RCN

Figure 7: Flipchart group 2 – FFG and VDI/VDE-IT

Figure 8: Flipchart group 3 – UEFISCDI and CDTI

Annex 3: Screenshots TAFTIE Workshop 2

TAFTIE workshop part 2: pilot info in a nutshell

UEFISCDI, Citizen participation in the new National R&D Strategy 2021 - 2027

Participatory activity	Number of persons reached	Related ethical challenges	How did the framework help to identify and overcome the challenges
Citizen workshop	60	Identifying and clarifying the expected contributions	We have been very clear and transparent about both the process and the potential impact of the participants output
		Planning the participatory process	We have been flexible and worked on the participants feedback and the vibe of the first event. We have also designed a friendly format and an informal set-up to help engage the participants
		Participants recruitment	We have had several discussions about which categories to be involved in the process and we have come up with a balanced and fair set of recruitment criteria
		Providing a meaningful and equal dialogue	We have had a fair and diverse representation. The actual event format was a significant and supportive tool in ensuring an equal and fruitful interaction
		Vulnerability of some of the participants	The design of the workshop and the experience and professionalism of the facilitators who have continuously reestablished any potential power imbalances

Figure 9: UEFISCDI ethical challenges

TAFTIE workshop part 2: pilot info in a nutshell

FFG, Citizen participation in topic definition

Participatory activity	Number of persons reached	Related ethical challenges	How did the framework help to identify and overcome the challenges
Citizen panel	30	Bias in participation (e.g. no marginalised groups represented)	Framework supported with diversity check .
Interviews with experts and stakeholders	13	Transparency of the process and expectation management. The challenge was met by defining the Informed consent accordingly.	Overall, the framework helped in reflecting and defining the pilot.
Validation workshop	14	Transparency of the process and expectation management. The challenge was met by being very transparent on the aims of the study and the specific workshop.	See above.
Online Survey to reach out to citizens	123	We did a lot of thinking on how to reach out to citizens . We decided to use many channels to reach out to persons and to allow for a self-selection bias . It was challenging to render the questions in a way so that people could understand them without problems, while at the same time allowing us to receive enough input so that our study is informed.	See above. When it comes to very specific challenges that are related to reaching out to citizens or to methodological challenges, the framework does not provide help (How to reach out to citizens? What questions can you expect them to answer? What depth of input can you expect them to provide? How to address them? What are the minimum standards that should be met in a participatory process within funding agencies?)

Figure 10: FFG ethical challenges

Participatory activity	Number of persons reached	Related ethical challenges	How did the framework help to identify and overcome the challenges
Citizen Advisory Board of Informal Caregivers	15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Putting together a diverse board • Bias in participation (more vulnerable participants have less time and resources to engage) • Strong opinion leader • Roles are not understood • Tension between over-engagement and possibilities of engagement/given structures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidelines for recruitment of diverse panels • Planning of the participatory processes, approaches and activities • Engaging participants

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Figure 11: VDI/VDE-IT ethical challenges

Participatory activity	Number of persons reached	Related ethical challenges	How did the framework help to identify and overcome the challenges
Focus group with program managers	4	How the internal formal or informal rules could affect the ethics of the participation.	Clear communication of goals and expectations from participants before the engagement activity is crucial, they must be aware of their role in the process
Interview with external institutional stakeholders	4	Selection of participants could be biased towards those institutions more linked to the CDTI	For the exploratory stage of the evaluation a low number of engaged institutions was required. For the data collection process all the regional agencies will be invited to participate, avoiding bias.
Interview with beneficiaries and consultancy firms	7	Avoid conflicting interests. There is an economic interest of participants in the CDTI as a funding agency. But this is out of the scope of this activity.	The use of the informed consent helps a lot to make clear the context of the participation and the relevant of ethics aspects that many times are ignored. It reflects respect for participants and defines the scope of their participation.
Interview with social stakeholders	4	How far from the traditional stakeholders should we go to measure in a proper and realistic way the social impact of the program?	Identify what knowledge is needed (scientific /technical background) for the participatory process.
Review of the evaluation questionnaire	13	Self-selection bias in the review of the questionnaire could affect the data collection process. The opinion of the most engaged stakeholders would be given priority	Identify and clarify the expected contributions. The goal was to validate the questionnaire, and it was explained in the mail sent to stakeholders

Figure 12: CDTI ethical challenges

Figure 13: Miro board group 1.1

Figure 14: Miro board group 1.2

Figure 15: Miro board group 2.1

Legend: Topics in green, solutions in pink, gaps and recommendations in orange.

Figure 16: Miro board group 2.2

